

Twin Transition for The Timber Industry

Deliverable 5.1

5G-TIMBER Market Analysis Report

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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
APAC	Asia-Pacific
CLT	Cross-laminated timber
DRP	Deliverable Responsible Person
DT	Digital Twin
DCS	Distributed Control System
EECCA	Eastern Europe, Caucasus, and Central Asia
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eMTC	enhanced Machine Type Communication
EWP	Engineered wood product
EU	European Union
FBI	Forest Based Industries
HDF	High-density fibreboards
LVL	Laminated veneer lumber
MDF	Medium-density fibreboards
ML	Machine Learning
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communication
NPN	Non-public Networks
NSA	Non-Stand-Alone
OSB	Oriented Strand Board
PLA	Plant Asset Management
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QRM	Quality Assurance and Risk Manager
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
UCs	Use-Cases
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
WVC	Wood Value Chain

1. Executive Summary

This Deliverable D5.1 5G-TIMBER Market analysis report documents the work that has been carried out in T5.1 EU Landscape Market Sector Assessment, Impact and Sustainability that ran from M1 to M9. The deliverable summarises the following aspects of the project a) a market analysis for closely related vertical industries that the project aims to support and improve, b) an overall general framework of 5G technology and its features, and c) some early estimations of market potential for each of the Use Cases (UCs) categories and underlying UCs.

First, a general introduction to the 5G-TIMBER goals, its outputs, the projects use cases, and an overview of the deliverables is presented, along with connections to other project outputs and assets. This is followed by an overview of the developed 5G-TIMBER commercialisation methodology, which will be followed throughout the project to produce the output expellable commercial assets and opportunities. This document outlines the initial market analysis and technology monitoring for the 5G-TIMBER project, and its focus areas, during the first 9 months of the project. It starts by describing related project goals, the features of 5G technologies and the potential use cases that can be implemented under the remit of this project. It also explores the political factors surrounding the implementation of 5G and how they impact the adoption of the technology.

The document provides a comprehensive overview of relevant market sectors and key areas involved in the 5G technology ecosystem, with a particular emphasis on the projects areas of impact in the forestry and timber sectors, namely, Wood Industry, Wood Materials, Sawn wood, Wood Energy, Composite Wood Materials, Wood Based Panels, Modular Construction Markets, Construction Technology Markets, and Smart Manufacturing.

The document delves into the 3 core Use Case categories of the project: "Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup", "Modular wood-house factory and Construction", and "Renovation with wooden elements and valorisation of composite waste". For each of these categories, the document provides a high-level overview and an early analysis of the role of 5G technology through the use of UC Categories PESTEL and UCs SWOT

analyses. The analysis also includes indications of the initial benefits imparted by 5G to the developed UCs along with some early thoughts on the potential industry related benefits derived for key actors. This vertical market assessment will be reviewed and evolved during the lifetime of the project (included in the business plan deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 at M18 and M36, respectively) and will be further informed by the ecosystem cluster and numerous partner activities in which all consortium members will share expertise. This vertical market assessment will act as a key foundation for any potential future commercial solutions that arise from the project.

2. Introduction

This Deliverable D5.1 5G-TIMBER Market analysis report documents the work that has been carried out in T5.1 EU Landscape Market Sector Assessment, Impact and Sustainability that ran from M1 to M9. This section provides the goal of the deliverable in the overall context of the 5G-TIMBER project, in addition to mapping the deliverable with the task it contained within. Furthermore, it also provides an overview of the document structure.

2.1. Mapping 5G-TIMBER Outputs

This section maps the components described in the 5G-TIMBER's Description of Action (DoA)/Grant Agreement (GA), i.e., the description of the deliverable and task description in the DoA/GA, against the chapters included in this deliverable and the justification of the work conducted in the project. See Table 1.

Table 1 Adherence to 5G-TIMBER's GA Deliverable and Tasks Descriptions

5G-TIMBER GA Element	5G-TIMBER GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D5.1	INITIAL MARKET SECTOR ANALYSIS AND IMPACT ASSEMENT.	CHAPTERS 5-9	CHAPTERS 5-9 ADDRESS THE CORE MARKETS AND SECTORS RELATED TO THE PROJECT GOALS, KEY TECHNOLOGIES AND SECTORS AND ADDRESS FOR UC SPECIFIC MARKET ASPECTS AND POSITIONING
TASKS			
T5.1 - EU LANDSCAPE MARKET SECTOR ASSESSMENT, IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY	T5.1 WILL PIVOT A MARKET ANALYSIS AROUND THE PROJECT'S PLANNED UCS, THUS INFORMING AND INCENTIVISING THE UCS TOWARDSTHE SPECIFIC MARKET NEEDS AND, LIKEWISE, KEEPING THE UCS ALIGNED WITH SECTORAL, INDUSTRIAL AND MARKET NEEDS. THE TASK WILL USE THE EXTENSIVE CONTACT NETWORK OF CONSORTIUM TO VALIDATE AND	CHAPTERS 5-9	CHAPTER 5 OUTLINES A GENERAL FRAMEWORK FOR 5G ROLLOUT, CHAPTER 6 OVERVIEWING THE 5G-TIMBER SPECIFIC WOOD MARKETS, CHAPTER 7 OUTLINING THE CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY MARKETS, CHAPTER 8 DISCUSSING THE SMART MANUFACTURING RELATED MARKETS AND CHAPTER 9

GROUND UC ASSUMPTIONS WITH A COMMERCIAL BIAS AND INDUSTRIAL NEEDS. THE TASK WILL INCLUDE MONITORING THE DEVELOPMENTS INTERNATIONALLY TO FULLY UNDERSTAND THE COMPETITION.

T5.1 WILL INCENTIVISE TASK 5.2'S BUSINESS PLAN, T5.3 IP PROTECTION.

DETAILING THE 5G-TIMBER MARKET POTENTIAL FOR THE PROJECT'S UCS.

2.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable addresses a structured market assessment of the related market for the 5G-TIMBER project. This introductory section provides an initial framing of the project details, the commercial goals (and related WP5 goals), the applications investigated in the UCs and the key features of 5G technologies and markets. Furthermore, the links with the other activities in this Work Package (WP) and the project (other WPs and tasks) are briefly identified below. The structure of the deliverable is therefore optimised to address the three UC categories considered in the project, namely "Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup", "Modular wood house factory", and "Construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste". Chapter 5 outlines a general framework for the overall 5G rollout, Chapter 6 details the 5G-Timber specific wood markets, Chapter 7 outlines the construction technology markets, Chapter 8 discusses the smart manufacturing related markets and Chapter 9 details the 5G-Timber market potential for the project's chosen UCs. These specific market inputs and positioning details are then linked to the outputs of the 5G-TIMBER project.

Prior to the above, Chapter 3 outlines the key background and project details related to the 5G-TIMBER project, with Chapter 4 overviewing the overall commercialisation processes proposed for the 5G-TIMBER project.

2.3. Other Project Outputs

This section describes the interdependencies with the other project tasks and activities.

- a) Interdependencies between the task of this deliverable and the other WPs:

- **WP2:** the technical developments carried out within the project (WP2) will be supported by D5.1.
 - **WP3:** the D5.1 will support detailed market inputs for the UCs and their ongoing development as conducted as part of WP3.
 - **WP4:** D5.1. will indirectly (through WP3) influence the deployment of 5G-TIMBER applications into the demonstration sites and the data collected.
 - **WP6:** Actions in D5.1 will influence the identification and engagement with stakeholder groupings and market demographics.
- b) Interdependencies between the task(s) of this deliverable and the same WP Tasks
- The business plan proposed in **T5.2-Business models development, commercialisation/business plan and commercial acceleration/sustainability** will be based on the market details described in D85.1.
 - Considering the different markets and segmentation identified here, **T5.3-Technology monitoring and IPR management and protection** will use these to map and monitor technology developments and IP opportunities.
 - Using the input of T.5.1, a stakeholder cluster and demographic target list will be used to help support actions in **T5.4-Commercial Ecosystem Cluster to accelerate commercial revenues and growth.**
 - In **T5.5-Standardisation recommendations**, standardisation contributions will be influenced by the needs and requirements of the identified demographics and market characteristics identified in D5.1.

Table 2 lists the other deliverables that **directly** consume outputs from this deliverable. In addition to the deliverables mentioned explicitly in **Table 2**, all the deliverables mentioned in the 5G-TIMBER’s DoA/GA will benefit from the content of D5.1. In particular, the deliverables related to WP5, WP6 and WP3/4 will take influence for the outputs of this document D5.1.

Table 2 Other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.

5G-TIMBER GA Element	Contribution and Value of linkage
Input for D5.2 and D5.3	Inputs on market need and market potential for further development of the projects business plans

Input for D5.5	Inputs on market needs and requirements for future potential patent filings
Input for D5.6	Inputs on indications of key targets for ongoing development of the commercial clustering actions
Input for D5.7 and D5.8	Inputs on indications of key area for standardisation contributions from the project
Input for D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3	Inputs on stakeholder grouping and targeting to the dissemination targeting actions
Input for D1.9	Inputs to setting of Final specification of functional and technical requirements of 5G NPN implementations for pilots and beyond
Input for D2.3, D2.5, D2.7	Inputs provided for market needs and direction for initial localised demonstrator functionality

3. 5G-TIMBER Project Background

3.1. Overview

The objective of the 5G-TIMBER project is to trial innovative data-driven material, production, and installation processes in four industries within the wood sector. This includes the development of 5G-powered use cases and implementation of field trials for small and medium-sized manufacturing industries such as small volume machinery, hand-assembled elements production, and construction using a wood value chain (WVC) as an example.

The project focuses on key areas of innovation such as:

- Timber material models
- Open standards for production data
- Secure data exchange
- Edge data analytics
- Precise indoor localization
- Digital Twin (DT) and augmented reality (AR)
- Industrial IoT

The goal of 5G-TIMBER is to support sustainable and efficient production, reduce waste, and increase recycling of wood-based materials. The project aims to promote the rapid adoption of 5G in real-life production environments and target a 50% increase in wood-based materials recycling, a 15% increase in productivity, 99% of factory work done, a 10% reduction in on-site work, a 10% decrease in product non-conformities, and improved safety for workers in the production and assembly of wooden houses [1].

5G-TIMBER aims to address the challenges in small-scale manufacturing and unlock the potential of the manufacturing sector with a focus on the wood industry by developing Industry 4.0+ toolkits for software and hardware open data-based applications. This will be achieved by deploying a 5G Non-public Networks (NPN), an interoperable blueprint for data sharing, sustainable, resilient, easily replicable, and scalable solutions for automation and digitalization. The project will implement a wood industry use case-driven approach, including examples such as sawmill machinery, wood house element manufacturing, construction and renovation, and wood waste valorisation (biochemistry).

The 5G-TIMBER project will be carried out through three interconnected phases, each following a cyclical process of development and testing. This iterative approach aims to confirm the effectiveness of the project's results in realistic settings and speed up the commercial adoption of its technological and network offerings. The project timeline consists of two successive testing cycles, starting with preparation and setup, followed by lab and field trials, and concluding with evaluations or redesign/improvement phases to maintain a consistent evolution of field trial validations. Full details of this can be found in Deliverable D1.1.

3.2. 5G-TIMBER Use Cases Overview

The project's UCs are clustered into three main categories:

1. Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup. This category will address the first part of the value chain of wood after forestry, starting with the cutting of the logs onwards to their processing in sawmills to produce lumber. The key focus of this category will be on the equipment used in sawmills, with key focus paid to the development, modernisation, setup, monitoring, remote operation, and maintenance of these systems.
2. Modular wood-house factory. This category will address the use of wooden parts in constructing modular pre-assembled modules of wooden buildings and structures. The key focus here will be on the production site where the modules are assembled (i.e. the factory) and the module components themselves. Modern technologies will be selected and integrated into the production process to help improve assembly efficiency, safety, and integration with utilized product lifecycle management tools.
3. Construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste. This category will focus on the remaining part of the life cycle of a wooden house, namely the building of it at the specific site and its ongoing monitoring during the use phase. The end-of-life stage will be focused on wooden composite wastes generated during the service life of the modules themselves.

Under these 3 core UC categories, a number of UCs will help focusing specific developmental work arising, with the full list of 5G-TIMBER UCs including:

- UC Cat 1- Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup.
 - UC 1.1 – Data and material models driven lumber production and handling
 - UC 1.2 –DTs assisted assembly, remote operation and servicing of woodworking machinery
 - UC 1.3 – Data and AI driven industrial machine’s fault prediction and design support
- UC Cat 2 – Modular wood house factory
 - UC 2.1 –Precise localisation for production processes optimization and human safety
 - UC 2.2 –DT, AR and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production supported by ZSM 5G data exchange
 - UC 2.3: Data-driven design to production cycle optimisation
- UC Cat 3 – Construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste
 - UC 3.1 –AR and Industry 5.0 UX-assisted assembly and renovation of green buildings
 - UC 3.2 –Long term SHM of wooden construction using IoT and embedded AI
 - UC 3.3 –Wooden composites waste recycling

The 5G-TIMBER project aims to carry out field trials utilizing the advanced features of 5G networks. To organize the trials, the project is structured based on the potential and strategic use of 5G technologies, as defined by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). The 3GPP has identified several potential markets and use cases for 5G and grouped them into families with shared requirements and characteristics, such as

1. Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB)
2. Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC)
3. Ultra-reliable Low-latency Communication (URLLC)

Additionally, new functionalities, known as vertical services, are being added to 5G technology specifications as part of 3GPP Releases 16 and 17. Of these, location services are particularly relevant to the 5G-TIMBER project. It should be noted that currently, only Release 16 of 5G technology will be supported in the scope of the 5G-TIMBER project and the actual use of its features will depend on the support in the RU and DU ecosystem. Therefore, projecting

allowed the partners to align the UCs, 5G Scenarios, and potential vertical services as seen in **Figure 1**. Full details of this can be found in Deliverable D1.1.

UC Category	UC	5G Scenarios			Vertical Services
		eMBB	mMTC	URLLC	LCS
1. Data driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup	1.1 - Data and material models driven lumber production and handling	✓✓	✓✓✓		
	1.2 - DTs assisted assembly, remote operation and servicing for woodworking machinery	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	
	1.3 - Data and AI driven industrial machine's fault prediction and design support		✓✓✓		
2. Modular wood-house factory	2.1 - Precise localization for production processes optimization and human safety	✓	✓		✓✓✓
	2.2 - DT, AR and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production supported by ZSM 5G data exchange	✓✓		✓✓✓	✓✓
	2.3 - Data driven design to production cycle optimization	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	
3. Construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste	3.1 - AR and Industry 5.0 UX assisted assembly and renovation of green buildings	✓✓✓		✓✓✓	
	3.2 - Long term Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of wooden constructions using IoT and embedded AI		✓✓✓		
	3.3 - Wooden composites waste recycling				

Figure 1 5G Scenarios, Vertical Services and 5G-Timber Use [1]

3.3. WP5 Goals

The overall objective of WP5 in 5G-TIMBER is to build a commercial scale-up and business plan for the project, based on the Lean Start-up Methodology approach encompassing the 4 main phases of : i) Customer Validation, ii) Solution Alignment, iii) Business Model Selection, iv) Growth Trajectory. This objective will work in conjunction with the goal of protecting any developed commercially sensitive and strategic IP through the filing of Patents that will underpin the business plan and help achieve a competitive go-to-market advantage for the project and partners.

The business plan and potential patents will allow the formulation of a potential exploitation and commercial scale up strategy, aimed at the end goal of establishing self-sustaining revenues and a sustainable commercial trajectory post project completion. This exploitation, commercial scale-up and business plan strategy will be anchored via robust market sector analyses ensuring a clear fit between the project outcomes and their target market. The main goals of 5G-TIMBER WP5 can be categorised into a number of main sections, namely:

- **Market Assessment**
The goal of this section is to assess the market, segmentation and technology progress aspects of the project into a clear starting direction, supporting and enhancing the project's chances for commercial success post competition.
- **Business Model Development and Planning**
The goal of this section is to identify, develop and integrate a viable business model and support the building of a business plan for the commercialization of the key outcomes arising from the 5G-TIMBER project.
- **Technology Monitoring, IP and Commercialisation**
The goal of this section is to produce and deploy a valid plan to identify and protect any viable intellectual property generated during the project and construct a potentially viable commercialisation strategy to exploit project's central innovations.
- **Commercial Ecosystem Clustering**
The goal of this section is to develop, launch and grow Timber Helix to commence the collection of an initial commercially focused ecosystem cluster to support ongoing and future project exploitation actions.
- **Standardisation Actions**
The goal of this section is to identify relevant standards and bodies, develop meaningful contributions to said standards and make recommendations to these standards based on the ongoing 5G-TIMBER body of work.

This WP has a total of 5 tasks for successful completion, these tasks being:

- T5.1 - EU Landscape Market Sector assessment, impact and sustainability
- T5.2 - Business models development, commercialisation/business plan and commercial acceleration/sustainability
- T5.3 - Technology monitoring and IPR management and protection
- T5.4 - Commercial Ecosystem Cluster to accelerate commercial revenues and growth.
- T5.5 - Standardisation recommendations

These tasks all contribute to the overall future potential viability and business planning actions for the commercial exploitation of the 5G-TIMBER project post project completion.

4. 5G-TIMBER Commercialisation Methodology

This chapter details the commercialization journey to be undertaken by the consortium, led by ICP as the commercialization partner for the 5G-TIMBER project. The chapter introduces the Lean Start-Up Methodology and its significance in aiding the commercialization process of early-stage ventures. It will also illustrate how this methodology is applied to the 5G-TIMBER project and the research, actions and contributions required by project partners to identify the commercial possibilities arising from this project.

4.1. The Lean Start-Up Methodology

The 5G-TIMBER project employs a specific technique known as the Lean Start-up Methodology in order to establish sustainable business models. This is achieved through a process of iterative experimentation, development, and prototype testing, with a strong emphasis on gathering customer feedback (**Figure 2**). The ultimate aim of this approach is to ensure that the project's ideas align with market demand and have the potential to generate viable commercial opportunities. This method is commonly used in the creation of new firms, products, services or processes and has proven to be successful in the commercialization of early-stage research. It can provide a clear path for the project to identify market-suitable products and services, bring them to market swiftly, and establish sustainable business models to support commercial activity.

Figure 2 The Lean Start-up Methodology

The Lean Start-up Methodology, which was first introduced by Eric Ries in 2011 [3], is a valuable approach for commercializing early-stage research. It focuses on iterative development, prototyping, and gathering customer feedback to reach product-market fit, where a proposed product appeals to

enough potential customers to create a viable commercial opportunity. It is widely used in the creation of new companies and products, but it can also have a significant impact in the commercialization of research. This methodology is popular in founder-driven and investor-oriented start-up companies, and has also been successful in European Research Project Consortia despite the complexities of multi-year, multi-country, and multi-functional partnerships. It provides a clear path for projects such as 5G-TIMBER to identify market-suitable products and services from their use cases and project outcomes, bring them to market quickly, and identify sustainable business models to support that commercial activity.

4.2. 5G-TIMBER Commercialisation Process

The process of turning innovative research and ideas into successful business products is a complex and challenging endeavour, with many obstacles to success. One of the primary reasons for failure is the lack of product-market fit, which refers to the mismatch between the product or solution developed and the customer's actual needs and wants. This is a significant risk in the nascent 5G applications sector, where while investment has already been made in the underlying 5G infrastructure, use case applications are much less well developed. If projects focusing on the direct application of 5G to established industries works towards creating solutions for problems that are not large enough to support a viable business, the result may be a perception of 5G as a technology searching for problems in industry applications, leading to scepticism about its value to operational industries and sectors.

To minimize this risk, many ventures in new or emerging markets adopt the Lean Start-up Methodology as a framework for developing early viability. This approach emphasizes the creation of a new product or service that meets the urgent needs of the market and solves the customer's business problems. At 5G-TIMBER, we have incorporated several key principles of the Lean Start-up Methodology into our use case evaluation process, well proven through direct application via ICP, to ensure the viability of our solutions in the marketplace.

ICP has integrated the customer-centric and hypothesis-driven approach of the Lean Start-Up Methodology into the specific constraints and

requirements of European research projects, resulting in a hybrid model that blends Lean principles with the demands of projects such as 5G-TIMBER. This methodology encompasses four crucial pillars, which are utilized to formulate a validated and commercially feasible plan for the most promising opportunities. The resultant model adopted is a hybrid of Lean-Start-up thinking and orientation as shown in **Figure 3**. For 5G-TIMBER we start with a high-level view of 4 pillars of the methodology, before moving towards a validated, commercially viable plan for those opportunities that are the most commercially attractive.

Figure 3 Hybrid Lean Methodology Process applied to EU-funded projects

The overall commercialisation goal, key questions, key tasks, methods, and tools employed in each phase are summarised in **Figure 4**. The central stages of the 5G-TIMBER process will be undertaken, namely Market Assessment, Customer Validation, Solution Alignment, Business Model Selection and Launch and Growth Trajectory, which are discussed in detail in the next chapter.

Phase	Market Assessment	Customer Validation	Solution Alignment	Business Model Selection	Launch and Growth Trajectory
Key Question	Identify key markets, actors, dynamics, volumes and financials	Segment and refine specific customer wants and needs	Define and align potential product(s) to target market	Select the most appropriate business model to acquire and retain profitable customers	Articulate a business plan for growth and sustainability
Key Tasks	Market Analysis & Segmentation Market Intelligence Review Quantitative Mapping	*Market / Stakeholder Analysis and Segmentation *Use Case focused Business Validation	*Agree product(s) to Commercialise with commercial leader(s) *Define Product and Service Portfolio	*Examine range of potential models *Align business model most directly aligned to commercial leader and early adopters	*Roadmaps - Financial, People, Product, Marketing, Sales, funding
Methods and Tools	Market Intelligence Partner Interviews Partner Reports/Data Sources	Questionnaires UC Leader interviews Post UC feedback	Product Definition Workshops Commercial Leader Workshops	Business Model Workshops Business Model Canvas, Value Proposition Canvas, PESTLE / SWOT analysis	Financial Templates Commercial Leader Interviews

Figure 4 Tasks, Methods and Tools in Commercialisation Validation

5. General Framework of 5G

5.1. 5G Features and Use Cases

The widespread rollout of 5G networks is expected to bring about a number of potential key benefits including eMBB with lower latency, URLLC and mMTC all supporting the potential for massive IoT, allowing for a virtually unlimited number of devices to be connected to the network at the same time. These key benefits are closely linked to the overall goals of the project, as seen previously in **Figure 1**.

The enhanced mobile broadband with ultra-low latency will provide consumers with a new level of mobile connectivity. While 5G speeds are projected to reach 1-20 Gbps, Deutsche Telekom has already tested 5G and achieved speeds of 3 Gbps [4]. This level of speed will make it possible for consumers to engage in Virtual Reality (VR)/AR experiences on-the-go, stream video in high-definition formats, such as 3D, 4K, 8K, and 360°, and experience high-density content. There is already evidence of an increased demand for data among private consumers; while in 2016, a typical consumer used 1.6 GB per month, this figure was expected to increase to 7 GB per month by 2021 [5]. Additionally, 5G will enable massive IoT, allowing for smart building meters and sensors, as well as industrial robotics and connected machines, to communicate with each other quickly and efficiently.

5G technology will also have important implications for the healthcare sector and medicine. The low latency and fast connectivity offered by 5G will make remote video diagnoses easier and facilitate remote-controlled surgeries, as well as improve guidance for practitioners. As an example, Barcelona has already launched a pilot project for remote surgery assistance utilizing 5G. Additionally, 5G solves the latency problem and provides ultrahigh definition, allowing for collaboration among remote locations around the world. The first 5G tele-mentored surgery was held in Barcelona on February 27th, 2019 .

The latest advancements in technology which brought about the introduction of 5G, which is set to widely replace 4G. One of the key

differences between these two technologies is the increased bandwidth and lower latency that 5G offers. Technical specifications of 5G include:

- eMBB – This feature provides high-speed connectivity ranging from 1 to 20 gigabits per second, as well as increased network capacity and more efficient use of bandwidth.
- URLLC – 5G offers lower latency of 1-3 milliseconds compared to 4G's 15-10 milliseconds, providing ultra-reliable and secure communication.
- mMTC – This aspect of 5G enables connectivity for up to 1 billion IoT devices per square kilometre [8].
- Core Network Approach – 5G will be initially implemented through Non-Stand-Alone (NSA) deployments, followed by Stand-Alone deployments. NSA will provide higher data bandwidth and reliable connectivity, but the full potential of 5G can only be achieved through SA deployment [7].
- Network Slicing – This new 5G architecture allows for network slices to be tailored to individual customers, providing unique sets of resources for connectivity, speed, and capacity. This can only be done in Stand-Alone 5G mode [8].
- NPN – 5G NPN refer to private 5G networks that are operated independently from public mobile networks [9].

5G NPN's are a key component of the 5G-Timber project, in this case acting as a private network, providing 5G network services exclusively to a specific user organization or a group of organizations. The NPN is therefore deployed on the premises defined by the organization, such as a factory or campus, as opposed to a network that offers mobile network services to the general public. Non-public networks are preferred for several reasons, including [9]:

- High quality-of-service requirements.
- Dedicated security credentials to meet high security requirements.
- Isolation from other networks to protect against public mobile network malfunctions.
- Accountability for availability, maintenance, and operation.

NPNs are designed to provide organizations with secure, reliable, and high-speed wireless connectivity for their internal operations, such as industrial automation, logistics, and critical communication services. In 5g-Timber NPNs will be deployed on-premises, or hosted by a third-party providers, and will be tailored to meet the specific needs of the organization aligning with the overall needs for the 5G-Timber project [9].

5.2. Politics in 5G

Even though actual 5G deployment has been quite successful in its implementation, there is substantial discussion and concern about its availability. In response, the European Union formed a Public Private Partnership between the European Commission and European ICT in an effort to tackle 5G challenges and shape the future of networks.

5G Concerns

The advancement of 5G technology has brought about debates and concerns about its implementation. One concern is the potential for difficulties in monitoring by law enforcement due to the scattering of data across many elements of the mobile system [10]. This was a topic discussed at the Prague 5G Security Conference held on May 2nd and 3rd, 2019, where experts in cyber security from the EU, NATO, and other countries along with 5G network experts met to address the opportunities for malicious activity enabled by 5G [11]. The meeting resulted in proposals being put forward in the areas of Policy, Technology, Economy, Security, Privacy, and Resilience.

Another issue surrounding 5G implementation is the perception of the tech company Huawei's leading role in the mobile network equipment provider industry. Some policymakers in Brussels believe that Huawei achieved this position through unethical practices such as espionage and price dumping. This has raised concerns about Europe's dependence on Chinese technologies, as opposed to their confidence in the US legal system. Unlike companies like Cisco that have a global network switch market share of over 50%, Huawei is not trusted to protect sensitive customer data from national security and intelligence services, as Chinese firms are obligated to collaborate with Chinese intelligence agencies [12,13]. This has resulted in the EU having to decide if the 28 5G network deals that Huawei has closed in European countries pose a risk to national security [14].

5G Rollout

In the European Union, the responsibility for the implementation of 5G falls on individual member states. As of 2019, 11 member states have already completed or will soon complete 5G auctions: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, the Netherlands, Lithuania, and Portugal. In addition, there are six more auctions planned for

2020 in Spain, Malta, Lithuania, Slovakia, Poland, and the UK. The 5G Action Plan sets a target for commercial rollout by 2020 and full implementation in cities and major transportation routes by 2025. The European Commission's 5G Public-Private Partnership has made Europe a leader in testing 5G verticals, with a total of 139 trials taking place. A key concern is cybersecurity, and all member states are expected to assess the risks associated with 5G deployment and develop guidelines for 5G network suppliers and operators to mitigate these risks [15].

5.2.1. 5G Business Ecosystem

Even though the adoption of 5G technology is increasing, 4G LTE will still be in use for a few more years. This is evident when looking at the projected number of 4G and 5G connections in mobile networks, as seen in **Figure 5**. By 2022, the Asia-Pacific region was expected to have the largest number of connections, with an estimated 3.85 billion 5G and 229 million 4G connections. In Western Europe, there were projected to be 678 million 5G and 74 million 4G connections, while North America expected to have had 589 million 5G and 102 million 4G connections by 2022 [16].

Figure 5 Number of Devices connected by Connection Type [16]

The market for 5G technology is expected to experience substantial growth in the coming years, with a projected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 111% between 2019 and 2025. By 2025, the market is estimated to reach a value of USD 277 billion [17]. In the field of telecom mobile infrastructure, the leading companies globally in 2022 were Huawei (USD 71.2 billion), Cisco (USD

26.6 billion) and Nokia (USD 9 billion)[18]. The overall market value for telecom infrastructure providers in 2022 can be seen below in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6 Ranking of telecom infrastructure companies by brand value in 2022 [18]

The expenditure in the telecommunications sector has been consistently increasing, with an estimated 3.2% growth in 2019[19]. In terms of the global spending forecast for telecom network infrastructure, the following figures (in billions of US dollars) for the period from 2018 to 2024 are predicted, as seen in **Figure 7** [20].

Figure 7 Forecast spending global telecom services 2018 – 2023 [20]

According to Gartner, the expected spending on 5G mobile infrastructure is estimated to reach 4.2 billion US dollars by 2020 [21]. In terms of user numbers, there has been a significant increase in active mobile broadband

subscriptions worldwide from 2007 to 2018, reaching a total of 5.286 billion in 2018 [22]. The composition of these subscriptions can be seen in **Figure 8** below.

Figure 8 Global Mobile Subscription Forecast (2017-2023), by technology [18]

The usage of 5G is expected to result in a significant growth in the amount of data transferred via telecommunication networks. In 2018, the average global monthly smartphone traffic was 25 exabytes/month, but by 2024, it is anticipated to reach 131 exabytes/month, which translates to an increase from 5.6 GB/month per person in 2018 to nearly 20 GB/month per person in 2024 up to an estimated 46 GB/month in 2028 [23]. This anticipated growth can be attributed to the increasing usage of cellular connected PCs, tablets, and smartphones, as well as an increase in M2M data amounts. The most widely used applications consuming this data are internet, video streaming, web browsing, online gaming, and file sharing, with internet video being the primary data user, as seen in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9 Global Internet Consumer Data Traffic worldwide, by segment (2016-2022) [18]

6. 5G-TIMBER Market Specific Analysis

The 5G-TIMBER project aims to demonstrate the use of data-driven techniques to achieve waste reduction and increased efficiency in the wood, construction, and machinery industries. This will be done through the application of DT technology, secure 5G communication, and artificial intelligence (AI) at the edge. Across the EU-27 (2018), WVC are 397000 enterprises representing almost 20% of the manufacturing enterprises in EU and employing 3.1 million people with a gross value added of EUR 139 billion, or 7.1% of the total manufacturing industry. The global market for wooden prefabricated housing is estimated to be worth EUR 73 billion in 2021, with a projected growth rate of 6.7% per year [24]. The EU market for wooden renovations is expected to reach EUR 32 billion in 2026, supporting a pledge by Housing Europe members to renovate 4 million houses by 2030 [25]. The Forest Based Industries (FBI) Vision 2050 [26] suggests that by 2050, wood, the most widely used renewable construction material, will have more than tripled its market share from 2015. Approximately 70% of all wood products are used for construction purposes [26].

As per the original project proposal, the launch of the 5G-TIMBER collection of applications is projected to result in an additional 15 million euros in revenue for participating companies and has the potential to bring in three billion euros if adopted in more than five other nations by the end of the project. The proposed toolkit has a broad range of exploitation opportunities across various industries. One of the highest commercial potentials of 5G applications in the manufacturing sector is in the use of DT technology. In 2020, the worldwide market for DT was valued at 5.04 billion dollars, and it is anticipated to grow at a compound annual rate of 42.7% from 2021 to 2028 [27]. The integration of DT into manufacturing, as well as the growing adoption of Industry 4.0 and IoT, presents numerous growth opportunities for players in the DT market and for the 5G-TIMBER project. These aspects allowed the focusing of the market assessment on the key areas of opportunity for the project, and thus the market analysis overall.

In 2021 the total export of timber and wood products from Russian Federation was valued USD 13.9 billion and the EU was a dominant export market [28]. After Russia's invasion to Ukraine in February 2022, the EU applied sanctions, including on wood imports from Russia and Belarus, to end that invasion. The

sanctions and insecurity about the future availability of materials caused the sharp rise of timber material prices in Europe. According to Harmet's purchasing manager, the timber material prices almost doubled compared to the prices before the invasion. Due to mentioned factors, several timber material sellers in Europe bought large quantities of materials to their stock. Surprisingly, Europe's timber consumers managed to re-route most of their supply chains keeping Russia and Belarus out.

Due to this, in the second part of 2022, the timber material prices fell remarkably, to about 110% of the price level before the invasion. As there was no deficit of timber material on the market, the companies who owned large stock in warehouse were ready to sell their material with zero marginal or small loss. According to Harmet, the wood material prices will increase soon when the existing stock supplies will be sold. The timber products with length over 5 meters are according to Harmet the only type of timber material, which price did not decrease in the second part of 2022, and which still has poor availability in the EU market. Therefore manufacturers and builders who do not want to pay higher prices have to either modify their project using shorter timber material or replace wood with other building material.

6.1. Wood Industry Markets

Key wood industry markets and sectors were analysed, in order to understand the market dynamics of each key sectoral area. The key source for this sector is the regular updates United Nations UNECE Forest Products Annual Market Review report, with the most recent version covering the 2021-2022 [28] period, acting as the central sources for EU wood industry activities and core figures. The market details related to the 5G-Timber project are discussed below.

6.1.1. Wood Materials

In 2020 the total timber harvest fell by 3.4% compared to 2019 in the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) region. The total 2020 harvest volume of 1.40 billion m³ consisted 82% of industrial roundwood and 18% of wood fuel. There was almost no change in the Eastern Europe, Caucasus, and Central Asia (EECCA) countries whereas the biggest drop was

in the North America. In 2020 the consumption of industrial roundwood decreased in the UNECE region to 1.12 billion m³ [28].

Europe: Coniferous industrial roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 10 European coniferous industrial roundwood production trade and consumption, 2016–2020 [28]

Europe: Non-coniferous industrial roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 11 European non-coniferous industrial roundwood production trade and consumption, 2016–2020 [28]

There has also been a decrease of 10% in the consumption of non-coniferous industrial roundwood – it fell to 229 million m³, which is the lowest number seen since 2009, as seen in **Figure 10** and **Figure 11**. The usage of coniferous industrial roundwood lowered only by 1.3% to 895 million m³ [28]. The leading exporter of industrial roundwood in the world is the UNECE region. From the industrial roundwood traded globally in 2020, UNECE region traded 78% of the coniferous and 58% of the non-coniferous industrial roundwood. The exports were in total 93 million m³, which is the highest number seen for 13 years. Over the last five years exports have increased for Europe (+53%) and decreased for the EECCA (-33%) and North America (-34%) [28], as seen in **Figure 12**.

Europe: Traded industrial roundwood unit value, 2016-2020

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 12 European industrial roundwood unit value, 2016-2020 [28]

Top five intra-European trade flows of coniferous industrial roundwood, 2020

Origin-destination	million m ³	Change 2015-2019 (%)
Czech Republic-Austria	6.3	110
Germany-Austria	3.2	78
Czech Republic-Germany	2.7	12
Norway-Sweden	2.6	8
Czech Republic-Poland	2.5	N/A

Source: Wood Resources International, 2021.

Figure 13 Top Five European trade flows of coniferous industrial roundwood, 2020 [28]

The largest exporters of industrial roundwood in the UNECE region in the descending order by volume are the following countries: the Czech Republic, the Russian Federation, Germany, the United States, Canada, Belgium, Poland and Norway, as seen in Figure 13.

In 2020, Europe’s output of industrial roundwood decreased by 2% to 426 million m³ after the output had increased for eight years in a row [28], as seen in Figure 10 and Figure 11. The drop was biggest in Finland, Italy, Poland, Austria and Slovakia. The sawlog prices rose in 2020 and early 2021. As seen in Figure 14, with the main driving sub-regions being Europe and North America with their strong sawn timber markets. Remarkable increases in price appeared in eastern and central Europe, also in west parts of Canada and the United States. A change took place in the United States in 2021 July and August as the lumber prices decreased remarkably. As the price of sawlogs had not actually reduced, the profits of sawmills in the whole country fell [28].

European Quarterly Sawlog Price Index, 1999-2021

Source: Wood Resource Quarterly, 2021.

Figure 14 European Quarterly Sawlog Price Index, 1999 – 2021 [28]

In 2020, industrial roundwood production in the EECCA remained consistent, producing a total of 228 million m³, including 182 million m³ of coniferous logs (Figure 15) and 46 million m³ of non-coniferous logs (Figure 16) [28]. Although the overall production and consumption remained steady, there were differences in trends between the various countries.

EECCA: Coniferous industrial roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: FAOSTAT, 2021.

Figure 15 EECCA Coniferous roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016–2020 [28]

EECCA: Non-coniferous industrial roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: FAOSTAT, 2021.

Figure 16 EECCA non-coniferous industrial roundwood production, trade and consumption, 2016–2020 [28]

In 2020 the total export of industrial roundwood from the Russian Federation rose marginally after the export of coniferous industrial roundwood had decreased for almost a decade. The export quantity on non-coniferous industrial roundwood has grown 80% since 2010 – up to 8.1 million m³ in 2020

[28]. The most remarkable growth in exports has taken place for pulp logs going to Finland and non-coniferous sawlogs going to China. The reduced timber harvest was caused mostly by the Covid-19 situation in the world, which disturbed the supply chains of logs.

Figure 17 EECCA traded industrial roundwood unit value, trade 2016-2020 [28]

In 2020, the average declared unit value for exports of coniferous industrial roundwood in the EECCA decreased by 14.1% to USD 63 per m³ [28]. The average declared unit value for exports of non-coniferous industrial roundwood also decreased by 7.4% to USD 60 per m³ [28]. Meanwhile, imports of industrial roundwood decreased by 25.9%, with the unit value of non-coniferous industrial roundwood dropping by 15.3% to an average of USD 75 per m³ [28]. However, the unit value of coniferous industrial roundwood increased by 8.7% in 2020 compared to the previous year, reaching an average of USD 89 per m³, as seen in Figure 17.

6.1.2. Sawn wood

Covid-19 caused an unpredictable demand for wood products in the United States in mid-2020 followed by the other countries around the world. The growth continued in 2021. In 2020 the three subregions of UNECE received varied results in the utilization of sawn softwood due to Covid-19: in EECCA countries the consumption fell by 5.1%, in Europe the usage dropped by 0.4% but in North America the usage rose by 3.5% [28]. The same variation was visible in the statistics of sawn softwood production: it decreased in the EECCA countries by 5% but rose in the North America by 0.8% and in Europe by 1.6% (Figure 18).

In 2020 the sawn softwood exports increased by 3.9% to 58.9 million m³ in Europe due to reduced domestic need and increased production amounts [28]. The average export prices in the first half of 2020 rose only by 0.8% which was followed by a fast rise of prices during the second half-year.

Figure 18 European sawn softwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020 [28]

A total of 47.3 million m³ of sawn softwood was produced by the EECCA countries in 2020. 29.8 million m³ of sawn softwood was exported by the Russian Federation in 2020. North America's outcome of sawn softwood was 101.6 million m³ in 2020. The export numbers fell in total by 5.2% to 28.2 million m³ – the drop happened in the United States by 15.2% and in Canada by 4.3%. The imports expanded to 26.3 million m³ (4.3%) and lumber prices were at their highest in May 2021 [28].

Despite the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, Europe saw a slight rise in the production of sawn softwood in 2020, totalling 114 million m³, an increase of 1.6% compared to the previous year (**Figure 18**). The production saw a boost, especially in the latter half of the year as sawmills recovered from reduced output in the early months of the pandemic.

Net apparent consumption of sawn softwood in Europe dipped by a small margin (0.4%) in 2020, reaching 95.9 million m³. The construction industry was relatively unaffected by the pandemic-related lockdowns, and the DIY sector saw an increase in demand as people spent more time at home. Despite depleted sawmill inventories, actual consumption is believed to have risen in many countries during the year. While some countries, like Italy, experienced a decline in apparent consumption, others, like the United Kingdom, saw an increase of 1.6%. The impact of the pandemic varied greatly among countries, and its effects are still being felt in the European and global markets in 2021.

Europe: Change in sawn softwood consumption, by country, 2019-2020

Note: Countries with unchanged apparent consumption are not shown.
Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 19 European change in sawn softwood consumption by country, 2019-2020 [28]

The imbalanced supply and demand remains a significant issue (Error! Reference source not found.) [28].

The creation and utilization of sawn hardwood in the UNECE region suffered greatly in 2020 due to the Covid-19, Despite the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, consumption of sawn hardwood in Europe decreased by 4.8% in 2020, amounting to 13.6 million m³. Additionally, production of sawn hardwood also went down by 2.9% in the same year, reaching a total of 13.5 million m³, as seen in **Figure 20**. The overall utilization in the region fell by 18.3%. In sub-regions the decline was biggest in North America (27.7%), following EECCA countries (17.0%) and Europe (4.8%) [28]. The production of sawn hardwood decreased in 2020 in all sub-regions.

The biggest fall, percentage wise, took place in North America, where it fell by 24.7% to 17.7 million m³ followed by EECCA (by 15.9% to 3.64 million m³) and Europe (by 2.9% to 13.5 million m³), UNECE region’s total decrease was 16.5% [28]. In 2020 the imports of temperate and tropical sawn wood were ruled by China with 33.9 million m³ with an approximate value of USD7.6 billion. The international exports of sawn wood were controlled by UNECE countries led by Russian Federation and Canada [28].

Europe: Sawn hardwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 20 European sawn hardwood production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020 [28]

Europe: Traded sawnwood unit value, 2016-2020

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 21 European traded sawn wood unit value, 2016 – 2020 [28]

In 2020, the unit values of imported sawn hardwood remained consistent, with a decrease of only 0.6% compared to the previous year. However, the unit values of exported sawn hardwood declined by 4.2% (Figure 21). European hardwood sawmills heavily rely on the global hardwood market, as almost 45% of their production is exported. On the other hand, a considerable portion of hardwood lumber is imported, accounting for about 45% of Europe's overall wood consumption, with the source originating from other countries [28].

6.1.3. Wood Energy

Wood energy has an important part in the renewable-energy strategies of different UNECE region countries. In 2020 the creation and utilization of wood fuel shrank to 246 million m³ by 13.9 million m³. In the UNECE region commercial electricity production has caused big part of the recent additional demand for wood energy. In the future, demand might grow additionally due to higher needs for combined heat and power plus to provide material for industrial and residential heating.

Europe: Wood fuel production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 22 European wood fuel production, trade and consumption, 2016 -2020 [28]

A Eurostat report of 2020 indicates that in 2019, 23% of the EU27's roundwood production was utilized for energy generation, which is a considerable increase from the 17% reported in the year 2000. In Italy, Cyprus, and the Netherlands, close to 60% of roundwood production was directed towards energy generation [46]. The proportion of roundwood utilized for energy purposes saw a growth of 58% in the Netherlands and 52% in Cyprus between the years 2000 and 2019 [28]. The consumption of European wood fuel slightly decreased in 2020, by 1.5% as seen in **Figure 22**.

Europe: Wood pellet production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 23 European wood pellet production, trade and consumption, 2016 -2020 [28]

There is a steady growth in the usage of wood pellets – used in the residential heating and electricity and just hear production in the industrial sector. The UNECE region produces 80% of the whole world's wood energy and exports 90% of global quantities. In 2020 the annual production of wood pellets increased in the UNECE region by 4.8% reaching 35.6 million tonnes. In 2020 Europe was the biggest consumer and main exporter of wood pellets. In 2020, Europe

generated an estimated 22.5 million metric tons of wood pellets, with a slight decrease (0.3%) in imports compared to 2019, which totalled 21.7 million metric tons (**Figure 23**).

Europe is home to numerous companies that hold ENplus certification. Germany was the leading producer of ENplus-certified pellets worldwide in

2020, producing over 3 million metric tons, while Austria and Poland ranked second and third among Europe's producers (according to ENplus, 2021). In 2020, global production of ENplus-certified pellets was over 12 million metric tons, and is projected to exceed 14 million metric tons in 2021 [28]. The Russian Federation increased its wood pellet production annually by 6.5%. In 2020 the demand for ENplus-certified pellets was more than 12 million tonnes and the demand is growing.

Sustainable and renewable energy policies continue to shape wood-energy systems in Europe and United States. The biggest global producers of wood pellets in decreasing order are United States, Canada and Vietnam. Vietnam is also the second largest exporter of wood pellets after the United States, producing in 2020 almost 3.1 million tonnes for export. The two biggest importers of wood pellets outside of the UNECE region in 2020 are the Republic of Korea importing 3 million tonnes and Japan importing 2 million tonnes annually [28].

Global top ten wood fuel and wood pellet exporters, 2020

	Wood fuel		Wood pellets		Total
	1,000 m ³	\$ million	1,000 tonnes	\$ million	\$ million
United States	366*	21.7*	7,257	982	1,004
Latvia	490	58,9	2,350	373	432
Canada	110	4.7	2,901	406	410
Viet Nam*	3	0.4	3,077	309	310
Russian Federation	175	8.9	2,294	290	299
Estonia	206	19	1,070	184	203
Denmark	46	1.3	1,064	194	195
Austria	11	0.9	848	192	193
Germany	166	7.3	751	182	190
Lithuania	318	32	610	112	144

Note: * 2019 data.

Sources: Comtrade, 2021; FAOSTAT, 2021; UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 24 Top 10 wood fuel and wood pellet exporters, 2020 [28]

6.2. Composite Wood Products

Composite wood products can consist of a number of different products and arrangements. The UNECE report divides these into two classes:

1. Wood based panels and

The biggest exporters of wood fuel and pellets (taking into account both value and volume) outside of UNECE region is Vietnam (Figure 24). Latvia is the leading exporter of wood fuel in terms of both volume and value, with the United States coming in second place for volume and value. The United States is the leading exporter of wood pellets in terms of both volume and value, with the Canada coming in second place for volume and Vietnam for overall value.

2. Value-added wood products with a sub-category of engineered timber products.

This study utilises the following classifications, based on the UNECE structure, 1. Wood based panels and 2. Engineered timber products. This ensures that these sector align with both UNECE standard practice, but also the overall goals of the 5G-Timber project.

6.2.1. Wood-Based Panels

In 2020 there was a continuous decline in UNECE's wood-based panel industry caused mainly by the Covid-19 impact on the regions' economies: the manufacturing fell by 3.3% and the consumption by 4.3%. There was a fall in the consumption of both non-structural panels (by 5.6%) as well as structural panels (by 2.2%). The real GDP in the EU27 was -6.1% in 2020 meaning that the Europe's total wood-based panel production had better results (+3.1%) [28]. This was caused mainly by steady construction sector and firm recovery of the furniture production during the last six months of the year. The bigger production of oriented strandboard (OSB) by 3.5% somewhat balances the fall of manufacturing of other panel types [28].

In 2020 the production of wood-based panels in EECCA decreased to 23.4 million m³ (by 3.4%) and the usage fell to 19,0 million m³ (by 6.7%). In the Russian Federation the number of wood-based panels produced annually fell to 17.4 million m³ (by 1.0%). In North America the usage of wood-based panels dropped by 3.3% in 2020 regardless of the remodelling activities and improvement in the housing starts in the United States. In 2020 North America's structural panel industry's production capacity rose marginally (0.3%). The prices of structural panels increased to unprecedented levels due to the combination of strong demand and Covid-19 related impacts on supply chains. The main exporters of tropical plywood are China, Indonesia and Malaysia. Vietnam is not amongst the biggest exporters but managed to increase the export of tropical plywood in 2020 by 32% due to the increased demand in the United States. Japan is the largest global importer of tropical plywood. In 2020 Japan imported 29% less tropical plywood than in 2019 whilst the proportion of domestic plywood rose to 67% of total usage of plywood [28].

While overall consumption of primary forest products declined modestly in all general categories in the UNECE region in 2020: they fell by 4.3% for wood-based panels (**Figure 25**) while only by 3.3% for industrial roundwood; by 1.9% for sawn wood and by 3.9% for paper and paperboard [28].

	(1,000)	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Change (volume/ weight) 2019-2020	Change (%) 2019- 2020	Change (%) 2016- 2020
Wood-based panels									
Europe	m ³	71,704	74,210	75,854	74,961	71,528	-3,432	-4.6%	-0.2%
EECCA	m ³	16,687	18,351	21,204	19,364	18,204	-1,160	-6.0%	9.1%
North America	m ³	54,270	56,603	54,771	55,249	53,421	-1,827	-3.3%	-1.6%
Total	m ³	142,662	149,165	151,829	149,573	143,154	-6,420	-4.3%	0.3%

Note: Sawnwood does not include sleepers through 2016. Wood-based panels do not include veneer production.

Sources: FAOSTAT, 2021; UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 25 Consumption of wood-based panels in UNECE region by subregion, 2016-2020 [28]

In 2020 the biggest end-user of the wood-based panels in Europe was the furniture industry. The proportion of wood-based panels produced in Europe, which were used by the furniture sector, fell from 49% in 2019 to 47% in 2020. The building industry, which was less influenced by the pandemic than the furniture sector, used 38% of all the wood-based panels produced in Europe in 2020. As the structural panels are used more in the construction industry, Europe's market grew by 1.4% in 2020 whereas the market of non-structural panel market decreased by 2.8% [28], as seen below in **Figure 26** and **Figure 27**.

In EECCA the wood-based panel market was one of the least influenced sectors in 2020. Nevertheless, in Russian Federation the production of wood-based panels and furniture fell by 40-50% in April and May 2020 during the lockdown of pandemic crisis and many wood-based panel production plants were closed entirely. A big deficit of different types of wood-based panels such as flooring materials, high-density fibreboards (HDF), medium-density fibreboards (MDF), laminated or without particle boards, happened in the Russian market in the third quarter of 2020. The deficit caused by the pandemic together with shutdowns of factories unrelated to Covid-19 explains why the prices approximately doubled in August 2020. Higher market need for wood-based panels was caused by both seasonal interest and interest which is unique to 2020. The remarkable price increase of wood-based panels in North America was caused by the strong demand and

supply challenges due to Covid-19 during 2020 and the first part of 2021. By mid-2021, the prices of the following wood-based panels had increased enormously: western plywood by 417%, southern plywood by 377%, OSB by 455%. The price increases of particle board by 21% and MDF by 23% were less tremendous [28].

Europe: Structural panels production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 26 European structural panels production, trade and consumption, 2016–2020 [28]

Europe: Non-structural panels production, trade and consumption, 2016-2020

Note: Exports are shown as negative numbers.

Source: UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 27 European non-structural panels production, trade and consumption, 2016 – 2020 [28]

The biggest importers of wood-based panels (taking into account both value and volume) outside of UNECE region are Japan, China and Republic of Korea (**Figure 28**). China is the leading exporter of wood-based panels in terms of both volume and value, with Canada coming in second place for volume and Germany for value. Out of the top ten exporters globally, five are located within the UNECE region (**Figure 29**). Japan and the Republic of Korea are major importers of tropical plywood outside of the UNECE region, while Indonesia and Malaysia lead in terms of exports. In 2020, the UNECE region consumed 35% of all tropical plywood imports. However, imports to EU countries declined compared to 2019, while imports to the United States rose dramatically, making up 25% of global imports in 2020, up from just 11% in 2016 [28].

Top ten extraregional wood-based panel importers, 2020

	Structural	Non-structural	Total (all panels)	
	1,000 m ³	1,000 m ³	1,000 m ³	\$ million
Japan	2,122	723	3,080	1,643
China	1,213	1,626	3,191	1,040
Republic of Korea	1,787	1,273	3,173	960
Malaysia*	1,022	654	1,676	362
Mexico*	609	621	1,230	498
Viet Nam*	656	572	1,228	531
Egypt	792	507	1,299	372
Philippines*	925	194	1,119	507
Saudi Arabia*	443	721	1,165	435
Australia	488	241	754	478

Note: * 2019 data; UNECE region countries are not included.

Sources: FAOSTAT, 2021; UN Comtrade, 2021.

Figure 28 Top 10 extra regional wood-based panel importers, 2020 [28]

Top ten wood-based panel exporters globally, 2019

	Structural	Non-structural	Total (all panels)	
	1,000 m ³	1,000 m ³	1,000 m ³	\$ million
China	9,607	2,325	12,073	5,221
Canada	5,794	1,589	7,383	2,700
Russian Federation	3,266	3,048	6,315	1,807
Germany	874.07	5,131	6,005	2,758
Thailand*	54	5,401	5,456	972
Brazil	2,783	1,313	4,285	989
Belarus	906	2,468	3,374	585
Malaysia*	1,775	1,538	3,313	1,180
Poland	645.74	2,610	3,256	1,053
Indonesia*	2,732	519	3,251	1,813

Note: * 2019 data.

Sources: FAOSTAT, 2021; UN Comtrade, 2021; UNECE/FAO database, 2021.

Figure 29 Top 10 wood-based panel exported globally, 2019 [28]

6.2.2. Engineered Timber Products

Wood products, which are further processed into secondary products are called value-added wood products – such as furniture, profiled wood, engineered wood products, builders' joinery and carpentry. Engineered wood products (EWPs) are for example I-beams, glulam, laminated veneer lumber (LVL), finger-jointed sawn wood and mass timber panels including cross-laminated timber (CLT). The Covid-19 crisis caused the demand of EWPs to rise as people had suddenly more time to do something themselves including and as much time was spent at home, many started to renovate or expand their homes [28].

Glulam

The information about glulam manufacturing and utilization is not organized in the UNECE region. Therefore, complete statistics for UNECE and its subregions Europa and EECCA are not available. In replacement, the UNECE utilised focused country details by way of indicative figures, giving a logical baseline [28]. The biggest global producer of glulam in 2020 is Austria with estimated 1.59 million m³ in 2020 [47]. The second biggest producer is Germany with estimated 1.32 million m³. The main importer of UNECE region's glulam is Japan, who's imports rose in 2020 to 398000 m³ by 15.4%. The main three glulam suppliers to Japan are Finland (238000 m³), Romania (61700 m³)

and Estonia (50400 m³). In 2020 Europe reduced the import of glulam by 40% importing only 35000 m³ in a year. The available statistics from North America, as seen in **Figure 30**, indicate that in 2009 the annual production was 285000 m³ and the production has grown steadily and regularly between 2010 and 2019. In 2020 the manufacturing declined first time after a decade by 3.6%, as seen in **Figure 30**.

	2019	2020	2021(f)	Change 2019-2020
	(1,000 m ³)			(%)
United States				
Production	431	414	448	-3.9
Total consumption	435	419	452	-3.9
Residential	263	257	300	-2.3
Non-residential	155	146	135	-5.9
Industrial, other	17	15	17	-3.9
Inventory change	-5	-5	-5	
Canada				
Production	35	35	35	
North America, total production	466	449	483	-3.6

Note: f = forecast; 1 m³ = 650 board feet; Canadian imports are assumed to be minimal.

Source: APA, 2021a.

Figure 30 Glulam production and consumption, North America, 2019–2021 [28]

	2019	2020	2021(f)	Change 2019-2020
	(1,000 m ³)			(%)
Consumption				
I-beam flanges	561	592	702	5.6
Beams, headers, other	1,532	1,543	1,699	0.7
Total consumption	2,093	2,135	2,401	2.0
Production				
United States	1,909	1,954	2,208	2.4
Canada	184	181	198	-1.5
Total production	2,093	2,135	2,407	2.0

Note: f = forecast; 35.315 cubic feet = 1 m³.

Source: APA, 2021a.

Figure 31 Laminated veneer lumber consumption and production in North America, 2019–2021 [28]

Laminated Veneer Lumber

As for glulam, the information about glulam manufacturing and utilization in the UNECE region is scattered. In North America, LVL is used in the construction of new homes. In the year 2021, it was projected that 71% of the total volume of LVL will be utilized for applications such as beams and headers, rim boards and similar products, while the remaining amount will be used for I-joint flanges. Rim boards play a crucial role in I-beam floor systems by providing anchoring points for I-beams and also help in distributing loads from walls. The production of LVL reached its highest point in 2005 when the housing market in the United States was thriving, with a production volume of 2.6 million m³ [28]. Since then, the production has declined along with the I-beam production and the housing market. It was estimated that a total of 2.4 million m³ of LVL will be produced in 2021, which would be the fourth highest annual production volume ever recorded in North America [29]. A rough estimate of

laminated veneer consumption and production in North America can be seen above in **Figure 31**.

Cross-laminated timber

In 2020 2.8 million m³ of CLT was manufactured globally, from which 48% was produced in Europe, 43% in North America, 6% in Oceania and 3% in Asia [30]. The estimated production capacity in 2020 was 2.8 million m³. The capacity continues to grow and is expected to meet 4 million m³ by 2025. The following five countries produced in 2020 altogether more than 1 million m³ of CLT: Germany, Italy, Switzerland, the Czech Republic and Austria. This is a 15% rise since 2019.

North America has seen a growth in mass timber products production in recent years. As of 2018, ten CLT manufacturing plants were operating in both Canada and the United States, with a combined annual production capacity of 400000 m³ [31]. In 2021, the number of plants producing mass timber panels in North America has increased to 15, with an additional three under construction and three more planned. The current production capacity of these plants is estimated at 1.7 million m³, although most of this production is currently used for non-structural applications such as industrial matting. The practical capacity of CLT production for structural applications in buildings in North America was 439000 m³ in 2019, which is expected to rise by another 62000 m³ in 2021, excluding new proposed plants [31]. A rough estimate of actual CLT capacities for structural applications can be seen in **Figure 32**.

Company	Location	Estimated CLT production capacity (1,000 m ³)
DR Johnson Wood Innovations	Oregon, United States	280
Element 5	Ontario & Quebec, Canada	50
Freres	Oregon, United States	96
Kalesnikoff	British Columbia, Canada	50
Katerra	Washington, United States	185
LEAF Engineered Wood Products	Ontario, Canada	...
Nordic Structures	Quebec, Canada	80
Smartlam North America	Montana & Alabama, United States	70
Sterling Solutions	Illinois & Texas, United States	...
StructureCraft	British Columbia, Canada	...
Structurlam	British Columbia, Canada	70
Texas CLT	Arkansas, United States	...
Vaagen Timber	Washington, United States	25

Sources: Beck Group, 2020; Brandt et al., 2021; Forest Business Network, 2020; Katerra, 2020.

Figure 32 Estimated CLT production capacity for structural applications of North American manufacturers, 2020-28

6.3. Modular Construction Market

Specific market related data for the target market was gathered via utilisation of Market and Markets data, with access provided by ICP. The worldwide modular construction Market growth has been driven by the rising

global demand for affordable housing in all global regions, a desire to reduce waste and emissions and a push towards more sustainable construction methods. In 2020, the global market size for modular construction was estimated to be US 81.79 billion, with large growth predicted in Europe leading to estimated CAGR of 5.7% over the period 2020-2025 [32], as seen in **Figure 33**, to a total value of US 108.8 billion in 2025. On a square foot-built basis, an estimated 526.6 million square feet¹ was produced in 2020, predicted to grow further to an estimate 685.1 million square feet in 2025, growing at a CAGR of 5.40% during this period [32].

Figure 33 Global Modular Construction Market 2020- 2025 [32]

The growth of this market is to be driven by rising global housing shortages, increasing construction demand and overall increasing population growth and resultant urbanization. The largest region of future potential growth is the APAC market, with rapidly growing needs for housing supply, delivered at a fast pace. Government initiatives and support for fast build housing units, new technology innovations and smart building additions will all support rapid growth in this sector.

The Figure 34 Modular Construction Market, By Material in USD 2020 and 2025 [32]

The largest modular construction market by material is the wood material sector, with market share unchanged up to 2025, showing the dominance of wood materials over both concrete and steel in modular home construction applications, as seen below in **Figure 34**.

¹ One square foot is ca. 0.092 square meter

Segmentation by type in the sector, **Figure 35**, shows that permanent modular structures are by far the largest sector, with a market size predicted to be in excess of USD 80000 million by 2025, with the relocatable modular construction sector much smaller with, a market size of less than USD 30000 million predicted by 2025 [32].

Figure 35 Modular Construction Market by Type (USD million) [32]

Segmentation by end user type, **Figure 36**, shows that the largest sector is the Residential end user market, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 50000 million by 2025, up from a market size of just over USD 40000 million in 2020. All other sectors present much smaller end user opportunities, with smaller applications found in Office, Education, Retail and Commercial, Hospitality and Healthcare segments, with all of these predicted to have market sizes under USD 25000 million by 2025.

Figure 36 Modular Construction Market by End User (USD million) [32]

Geographically, growth in the modular construction sector, as seen in **Figure 37**, will be led on a total market size basis by Europe, growing to a market of USD 46299.3 million in 2025 (at a CAGR of 4.3%) and on a CAGR basis by Asia-Pacific at a 7.09% rate (to a market size of USD 39720.7 million) to 2025. Smaller growth rates will be seen in North America, USD 17548.3 million and CAGR of 6.75% to 2025, in Middle East and Africa, USD 3475.4 million and CAGR of 6.47% to 2025 and finally in South America, USD 1826.1 million and CAGR of 6.01% to 2025 [32].

REGION	2018	2019	2020	2025	CAGR
ASIA-PACIFIC	26,952.8	28,869.8	28,206.3	39,720.7	7.09 %
MIDDLE EAST AND AFRICA	2,476.3	2,622.4	2,539.8	3,475.4	6.47 %
NORTH AMERICA	12,347.6	13,183.1	12,690.5	17,548.3	6.7 %
SOUTH AMERICA	1,338.3	1,411.3	1,363.8	1,826.1	6.01 %
EUROPE	37,903.1	39,412.5	37,517.2	46,299.3	4.3 %

Figure 37 Modular Construction Market by Region (USD million) [32]

Segmentation of the modular construction market, **Figure 38**, shows that the wood segment is the largest segment, growing from 245.1 million square feet in 2020, at CAGR of 5.25% to an estimated 316.5 million square feet to 2025, followed by Concrete, growing from 187.2 million square feet in 2020, at CAGR of 4.87% to an estimated 237.5 million square feet by 2025, followed lastly by Steel, growing from 94.3 million square feet in 2020, at CAGR of 6.81% to an estimated 131.2 million square feet by 2025 [32].

Source: Industry Journals, Company Websites, Company Publications, Secondary Literature, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 38 Modular Construction Segment Growth Rate (million square feet) [32]

Segmentation of the modular construction market by application sector, as seen Figure 39, shows that the Residential sector is the largest sector in both 2020 and 2025, at 155.9 million square feet and 193.7 million square feet respectively, growing at a CAGR of 4.44% over that period. All sectors are predicted to grow, with significant CARG seen in the Office sector (6.62%), Retail and Commercial (6.35%) and Healthcare (7.89%) sectors. As in 2020, the dominate sectors of interest and application in 2025 are in the Residential (193.7 million square feet), Office (145.6 million square feet), Retail and Commercial (77.4 million square feet) and Other (162.6 million square feet) sectors [32].

Source: Research Journals, Related Publications, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 39 Modular Construction Segment Growth Rate by Application (million square feet) [32]

Geographically, this growth in the modular construction market will be led by large global economies, as seen in Figure 40, including China (8.38% CAGR), Poland (7.49% CAGR), India (6.93% CAGR), United States (6.47% CAGR) and Brazil (5.82%) or wealthy emerging economies such as UAE (7.52% CAGR) and Saudi Arabia (7.07 CARG). All other global regions are expected to see market growth from 2020 to 2025, but with CAGRs led than 6% expected in all other regions over that period.

Figure 40 Modular Construction Growth Rate by Region (CAGR) [32]

On an export basis, as seen in Figure 41, the production and export of prefabricated buildings is led globally by China (2091945 thousand USD), with a significant lead over the following countries Netherlands (778218 thousand USD), Estonia (600747 thousand USD), Czech Republic (596637 thousand USD), United States (497154 thousand USD), Germany (453321 thousand USD), Belgium (408928 thousand USD), Italy (385344 thousand USD), Lithuania (339083 thousand USD) and Slovenia (319099 thousand USD). This shows key production sectors, regions and outputs, with Northern and Central Europe well represented among the major export actors.

Figure 41 List of exporter of Prefabricated buildings, whether or not complete or already assembled, in 2021 [32]

The market dynamics of the Modular Construction Market (**Table 3**) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 3 Market Dynamics for Modular Construction Market [32]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing work zone safety & building sustainability • Need for time-saving and cost-effective construction • Ease of relocation of modular buildings • Supportive government initiatives
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of transportation and assembly issues in modular constructions
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population growth and urbanization translating to increased construction projects • Housing crisis in developed countries
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness in developing economies • Volatility in transportation charges

6.4. Construction and Demolition Waste Market

The global construction and demolition market growth has been driven by the growing construction and demolition waste from residential source. In 2021, the global market size for construction and demolition waste was estimated to be US 26.57 billion, with large growth predicted in APAC leading to estimated CAGR of 5.1% over the period 2021-2026, as seen **Figure 42**. On a weight basis, an estimated 4 112.6 million tons was produced in 2021, predicted to grow further to an estimate 5278.8 million tons in 2026, growing at a CAGR of 5.1% during this period. The fastest growing type of construction and demolition waste is concrete [33].

The growth of this market is to be driven by growing construction and demolition waste from residential source. The largest region of future potential growth is the APAC region with rapid urbanization and increasing spending in the building and construction sector. Emerging economies in APAC and South America have huge potential for market growth [33]. Covid-19 is expected to have an impact on the market as there is disruption in the building and construction and demolition sector and obstacles in the supply chain.

Figure 42 Global Construction and Demolition Waste Market 2021 – 2026 [33]

Segmentation by type in the sector, **Figure 43**, **Figure 35** show that soil, sand and gravel waste is the largest sector, with a market size predicted to exceed USD 12000 million by 2026, up from a market size of below 10000 in 2021. The second largest waste sector is concrete waste with a market size predicted to exceed 10000 million by 2026 and bricks and masonry waste predicted to reach almost USD 8000 million by 2026. All other sectors present much smaller opportunities found in metal, other waste and wood waste with all of these predicted to have market sizes under USD 2000 million by 2026 [33].

Figure 43 Construction and Demolition Waste Market by Type (USD million) [33]

Segmentation by construction and demolition waste source, **Figure 44**, shows that the residential source is the largest segment, growing from over USD 8000 million in 2021 to an estimated of almost USD 11000 million in 2026, followed by commercial source, growing from over USD 7000 million in 2021 to an estimated over USD 9000 million in 2026, followed by industrial source, growing from over USD 6000 million in 2021 to an estimated almost USD 8000 million in 2026 followed lastly by municipal source, growing from under USD 5000 million to an estimated over USD 6000 million in 2026 [33].

Figure 44 Construction and Demolition Waste Market by Source (USD million) [33]

Geographically, growth in the construction and demolition waste sector, as seen in Figure 45, will be led on a total market size basis by APAC, growing to a market of USD 21 914.6 million in 2026 (at a CAGR of 6.0%). Smaller growth rates will be seen in North America, USD 4985.6 million and CAGR of 4.3% to 2026, in Europe, USD 5869.8 million and CAGR of 3.9% to 2026, Middle East and Africa, USD 714.9 million and CAGR of 3.3% and finally in South America, USD 922.2 million and CAGR of 3% to 2026. In total the total market size is expected to reach USD 34407 million and CAGR of 5.3% by 2026 [33].

REGION	2019	2020	2021	2026	CAGR
ASIA-PACIFIC	16,640.0	15,485.8	16,344.0	21,914.6	6 %
NORTH AMERICA	4,229.7	3,878.4	4,032.4	4,985.6	4.3 %
EUROPE	5,143.5	4,686.1	4,841.5	5,869.8	3.9 %
MIDDLE EAST AND AFRICA	648.9	589.7	608.0	714.9	3.3 %
SOUTH AMERICA	812.9	773.2	796.2	922.2	3 %
TOTAL	27,474.9	25,413.2	26,622.1	34,407.0	5.3 %

Figure 45 Construction and Demolition Waste Market Size by Region (CAGR) [33]

Geographically, the growth in the construction and demolition waste sector, will be led North America, as seen in Figure 46, including Canada (4.6% CAGR) and United States (4.8% CAGR) and APAC economies including India (5.8% CAGR), China (5.6% CAGR) and Brazil (5.82%). All other global regions are expected to see market growth from 2021 to 2026, but with CAGRs less than 4.5% expected in all other regions over that period [33].

Note: CAGR is provided in terms of volume.

Source: Secondary Research, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 46 Construction and Demolition Waste Market Growth Rate by Region (CAGR) [33]

The market dynamics of the Construction and Demolition Waste Market (Table 4) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 4 Market Dynamics for Construction and Demolition Waste Market [33]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies related to construction and demolition waste • Rapid growth of construction industry in emerging economies of APAC, MEA and South America • Sustainable waste management and predicted waste
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ignorance towards construction and demolition waste management • Weak rules and regulations, along with illegal dumping of construction and demolition waste also factors
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation in the sorting and recycling technologies for the efficient treatment of construction and demolition waste • Growing adoption of construction and demolition waste materials in urban areas • Green building system promoting reuse and recycling of concrete elements and aggregates
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problems arising due to construction dust • Hindrance in workflow due to inefficiency of municipal bodies and local authorities

6.5. Wood Industry Markets Impact on the 5G-Timber Project

The overall wood market industry is a significant factor that could impact the 5G Timber project in several ways.

Firstly, the increasing demand for wood-based products such as wooden houses and furniture is driving the need for innovation and optimization in the wood manufacturing industry. The 5G Timber project's focus on improving efficiency, quality, and sustainability in wood manufacturing

processes can align with the industry's growing demand for high-quality, eco-friendly products.

Secondly, the incorporation of 5G technology and IoT devices in the wood manufacturing industry is relatively new, and its success will depend on the industry's willingness to adopt these technologies. However, the potential benefits of faster data processing, real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and remote control are likely to drive the adoption of 5G technology in the wood manufacturing industry.

Finally, the use of sustainable and eco-friendly practices in wood manufacturing is becoming increasingly important for consumers and businesses. The 5G Timber project's focus on sustainability through waste reduction, improved energy efficiency, and circular economy principles aligns with the growing demand for sustainable practices in the wood manufacturing industry.

7. Construction Technology Markets

This chapter includes market relevant information on the Building Information Modelling, AI, Augment Reality and Industrial Wearables and Smart Sensor markets, key influential markets for the proposed 5G-Timber solutions. Additional relevant market information for the Lidar and 3D Printed Buildings markets can be found in the Appendices.

7.1. Building Information Modelling

The global building information modelling (BIM) market can be attributed to the rising adoption of remote working caused by Covid-19, speedy increase in urbanisation globally, wide-ranging benefits of BIM being realized by the AEC industry and rising government initiatives to adopt BIM. In 2021, the global market size for building information modelling software was estimated to be US 5.9 billion, as seen in **Figure 47**, with large growth predicted in North America leading to estimated CAGR of 12.5% from 2021 to 2026 to a total predicted value of US 10.7 billion. North America is foreseen to have the biggest share of the building information modelling market in 2021 [34].

The growth in the infrastructure sector has helped the BIM market to grow at a significant rate. The software offering type of the building information modelling market is foreseen to have a bigger share during the forecast period. Product launches, collaborations and partnerships are predicted to offer advantageous opportunities for the market players from 2021 to 2026.

Figure 47 Global Building Information Modelling Market 2021 – 2026 [34]

Segmentation by end user type, **Figure 48**, illustrates that Architectural Design software is the biggest end user sector, with an approximate market size of USD 2390 million in 2026 growing from a market size of USD 1338 million in 2021. The Construction and Structures end users are on the second and third market size position, with approximate market sizes of USD 1321 million (Construction) and USD 1101 million (Structures) in 2026, growing from market

sizes of USD 796 million (Construction) and USD 632 million (Structures) in 2021. Other end user sectors (MEP, Facility Management and Sustainability) present a smaller market size – with approximate under USD 600 million in 2021 with predicted market size in 2026 below USD 850 million [34].

Source: Annual Reports, Press Releases, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 48 Building Information Modelling Market by User Type (USD million) [34]

Geographically, the building information modelling market share in 2021 was led by the United States who held 26% of the market, as seen in Figure 49, followed by China holding 14% of the market. Rest of the countries, who obtained a market share under 10%, in descending order are the United Kingdom (8%), Germany (6%), France (6%), Japan (5%), Canada (4%), Mexico (4%), South Korea (2%), India (2%), Italy (2%) and Spain (2%) [34].

Source: Annual Reports, Press Releases, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 49 Building Information Modelling Market Share in 2021 by Region (%) [34]

The market dynamics of the BIM Market (Table 5) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 5 Market Dynamics for BIM Market [34]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising adoption of remote working due to Covid-19 • Rapid rise in urbanization globally • Wide ranging benefits of BIM realized by AEC industry • Growing government initiatives for adoption of BIM
Restrains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High initial cost of BIM
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising trend of IOT in construction sector • Increasing trend of BIM • Growing focus of organizations on introducing new standards such as ISO 19650 in BIM market
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level of digitization in construction industry

7.2. Artificial Intelligence

In 2022 the estimated value of the AI global market was USD 119.8 billion. North America’s AI market size in 2021 was USD 147.6 billion. The global market size is predicted to reach USD 1 597.1 billion by 2030, with growth predicted in Figure 50.

Figure 50 AI Market Size, 2021 – 2030 [35]

The biggest market share in 2021, as seen in Figure 51, was owned by North America (42%), home of several well-known tech giants like Apple, Google, Facebook, Amazon, Microsoft and IBM. These companies have given valuable input to the development of North America’s AI market [35].

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MARKET SHARE, BY REGION, 2021 [%]

Figure 51 AI Market Share, By Region , 2021 [35]

In 2019, the president of United States established the American AI Initiative to stimulate US becoming the leader of the AI market. This initiative supported AI innovation in different industries and sectors and provided instructions for the real-life application of AI technology. The fastest growing AI market by 2030 is predicted to be Asia-Pacific (APAC). Different institutions in APAC are making increasing investments to adopt the AI which causes a rising demand for AI. The growth of AI market in APAC region is led by the growing adoption of AI in different businesses – such as healthcare, automotive, retail and food and beverage [35].

7.3. Augmented Reality and Industrial Wearables

In 2021 the estimated value of the global AR market size was USD 25.33 billion. US market size was estimated to be worth USD 7.8 billion in 2021, as seen in **Figure 52**, with it predicted to grow from 2022 to 2030 annually by 40.9% [36]. The growth of the market is driven by grown usage of smartphones and smart glasses and the related growth in adoption of the mobile AR technology with a goal to create a mesmerizing user experience. The growth of the market is also driven by the growing use of AR technology in architectural and constructional applications, where it gives a possibility to look at the planned projects on site in 3D before being actually built.

Figure 52 US AR Market, by size, 2020 – 2030 [36]

In 2021 the biggest revenue share of 33.9% was owned by North America and its market share is expected to grow as predicted. The United States owned the biggest share of the North America market being home to numerous big tech-companies including Google LLC and Microsoft. As Europe is leading the adoption of AR technology used for gaming and entertainment, its share of the market is expected to grow significantly.

APAC is forecasted to be the fastest-growing region from 2022 to 2030. Ongoing distribution of 5G networks in APAC region will also cause the boundless adoption of AR technology and solutions. On a market application level, as seen in Figure 52, the largest market is predicted to be in Industrial Manufacturing applications, followed by the automotive and Gaming and Entertainment application areas. Leading to an estimated value of the global AR market size of USD 25.33 billion for 2021 [36].

Figure 53 Global AR Market, by application, 2021 [36]

In 2019 the value of the global industrial wearables market was USD 1.1 billion and it is predicted to rise to USD 8.6 billion by 2024, growing annually 50.2%. The driving factors of the foreseeable market growth are connected to the high demand for effective collaborative working environment, grown interest of businesses in using AR technology specially in the production, VR technology for training and automation in production. The AR/VR glasses will most likely hold the biggest part of the industrial wearables market as these would transform different manufacturing industries significantly such as boosting productivity, shortening the downtime, ensuring quality [36].

The leading industrial wearables companies such as Google, Microsoft, Vuzix and Magic Leap, are based in the North America. Therefore, and as the industries in the North America are considered to be the early adopters of digitalization, North America is forecasted to be the driver of the industrial wearables market. The industrial wearables market is projected to grow from an estimated USD 1.1 billion in 2019, with a huge CARG of 50.2% to USD 8.6 billion by 2024, as seen in **Figure 54**, powered by the growing trends and popularity for Industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing processes [37]. Key sectors such as the automotive and manufacturing sector are embracing the use of wearable AR glasses for the provision of at hand information, computer aided guidance and training and the digitised collection of key data points during the application of detailed processes.

Figure 54 Industrial Wearables Market 2019 – 2024 [37]

On a regional basis, significant growth is predicted in all key regions, with the majority of this growth driven by the North American, Europe and APAC regions, while the rest of the world makes much more modest gains up to 2024. This growth is steady at an estimate CAGR of 50.2% over the period, as seen in **Figure 55**.

Figure 55 Industrial Wearables Market, by Region (USD billion) [37]

7.4. Smart Sensors

In 2022 the value of the global smart sensor market size was USD 45.8 billion. It is predicted to reach USD 104.5 billion by 2027 growing annually by 17.9% between 2022 and 2027, as seen in **Figure 56**. The driving factors of the predictable market growth are connected to the rising demand for smart sensors in consumer electronics and IoT-based devices, higher use of smart sensors in different industries including automotive industry and green construction and additionally the escalating usage of wireless technology to have overview of the security devices, which are supplied with smart sensors [38].

Currently the market is being led by North America which is being dominated by the United States. Europe holds the second biggest part of the market. APAC is the top potential growing market for market sensors in infrastructure, consumer electronics, automotive and pharmaceutical industries. By 2027 it is believed to be the biggest market for smart sensors with the main demand in Japan, China and India. China is a global production hub for different industries, which have shown a massive growth, and which produces for example computers, smartphones and home appliances. The potential growth is driven also by the rising foreign investments in manufacturing sector, growing population, low price of smart sensors and fast technological improvements in that region.

Figure 56 Global Smart Sensors Market, 2022 – 2027 [38]

7.5. Construction Technology Markets Impact on the 5G-Timber Project

The construction technology market is rapidly evolving with the emergence of new technologies, including 5G, IoT, AI, and XR. These technologies are being leveraged to improve safety, efficiency, and productivity in the construction industry. The 5G Timber project is at the forefront of this technological shift and is poised to take advantage of these advancements to improve the efficiency and sustainability of wooden house construction.

The project's focus on using 5G-based IoT devices, embedded AI, and XR technology for assembly, structural health monitoring, and recycling of wooden houses has the potential to disrupt the construction technology market. The adoption of these technologies could lead to significant improvements in safety, quality, and cost-effectiveness, giving the 5G Timber project a competitive edge in the market.

The market for sustainable construction materials, including wood, is growing, driven by increasing demand for eco-friendly, low-carbon alternatives to traditional building materials. The 5G Timber project's focus on sustainability aligns well with this trend, positioning the project to take advantage of this growing market.

Overall, the construction technology market's impact on the 5G Timber project is positive, with opportunities for the project to lead the market in the adoption of new technologies and practices.

8. Smart Manufacturing/Industry 4.0 Markets

This chapter includes market relevant information on the overall Smart Manufacturing and Industry 4.0 markets, covering Smart Manufacturing, Industrial Control and Factory Automation and Industry 4.0. Additional relevant market information for the Digital Transformation market can be found in the Appendices.

8.1. Smart Manufacturing

The global smart manufacturing market has seen steady growth via an ever-increasing emphasis on real-time data analysis and predictive maintenance leading to a boost in the technology enabling function of smart manufacturing processes. The smart manufacturing market was estimated in 2022, with projections made out to 2027, indicating an average CAGR of 18.5% from a market size of US 97.6 million in 2022 to an estimated US 228.2 million by 2027 [39], as in **Figure 57**. Rising demand for smart manufacturing technologies has stemmed from rapid expansion of end user industries, with a desire to further digitise operations. The largest region of potential is Asia Pacific, with the fastest growing information technology type existing in the warehouse management sector. Asia Pacific is expected to hold the highest market share globally during the forecast period, offering great opportunities for partnerships and lucrative deals for market players over the coming years.

Figure 57 Global Smart Manufacturing Markets 2022 – 2027 [39]

Key commercial leaders in the sector include star actors such as FANUC, ABB, KUKA, DENSO and Universal Robots, leading actions in this sector. These companies long established position make them suitable customers or commercial competitors in the sector. There also exist a number of emerging leaders in this area, with companies such as Seiko Epson, Omron Adept, Staubli, Siasun and Techman Robot all acting as potential collaborators, developmental partners or supporters to new innovations in the sector. These Star leaders, Emerging leaders, Participants and Pervasive actors are mapped below in **Figure 58**.

Figure 58 Key Actors in the Global Smart Manufacturing Sector [39]

Segmentation by application in the sector, **Figure 59**, shows that Manufacturing and Execution systems are the largest markets in both cases, with a market size predicted to be approximately USD 20000 million by 2027, up from a market size of approximately USD 12500 million in 2022. The second largest application is Plant Asset Management with a market size predicted to be approvals USD 10000 million by 2027. All other sectors present much smaller opportunities with both Human-Machine Interfaces and Warehouse Management Systems to have market sizes under USD 10000 million by 2027.

Figure 59 Smart Manufacturing Applications for Information technology to 2027 [39]

Segmentation by enabling technology in the sector, **Figure 60**, shows that DTs are to hold the largest size of the smart manufacturing market by 2027, with a market size predicted to exceed of USD 40000 million by 2027, up from a market size of below USD 5000 million in 2022. The second largest enabling technologies are predicted to be Industrial Sensors and Robots, with a

market size predicted to exceed USD 35000 million by 2027 for both technologies. All other sectors present largest grow rates up to 2027, but lower overall market sizes to 2027, as seen below, with CARG rates ranging from 68.9% for DTs down to 5.1% for Industrial Machine Vision [39].

Source: Expert Interviews and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 60 Smart Manufacturing market share, by application in 2027 [39]

Geographically, this growth in the smart manufacturing sector will be led by large Asian economies, as seen in Figure 61, including China (21.2% CAGR), and India (21.2% CAGR). Significant growth rates of between 18% and 20% are predicted for Mexico (19% CAGR), France (18.8% CAGR), Japan (18.7% CAGR), US (18.6% CAGR) and the rest of the APAC region (18.2% CAGR). Significant growth rates are predicted globally, with many major global economies predicted to grow above 16% CAGR to 2027 [39].

Figure 61 Global Smart Manufacturing Market Growth Rates [39]

The market dynamics of the Smart Manufacturing Market (Table 6) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 6 Market Dynamics for Smart Manufacturing Market [39]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising emphasis on smart manufacturing in manufacturing processes • Increasing government involvement in supporting smart manufacturing • Growing emphasis on regulatory compliances • Surging demand for software systems that reduce time and cost
Restrains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investments and costs involved in implementing smart manufacturing solutions • Lack of standardization among equipment manufacturers and in connectivity protocols • Requirement of maintenance attributed to frequent software upgrade
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in adoption of IoT and cloud technologies • Increase integration of different solutions to provide improved performance • Rapid industrial growth in emerging economies
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Threats related to cyber security • Complexity in implementing smart manufacturing technology systems • Lack of skilled workforce.

8.2. Industrial Control and Factory Automation

The global industrial control and automation Market is predicted to grow to 2027 due to the rising need for mass manufacturing of products and an increasing number of government programs to promote enhanced industrial automation actions, with the market estimated in 2022, with projections made out to 2027, indicating an average CAGR of 8.2% from a market size of US 147.9 billion in 2022 to an estimated US 218.8 billion by 2027 [40], as in **Figure 62**. The largest region of potential is Asia Pacific, with the fastest growing vertical being the Discrete Application industry. The largest markets is presently found in China and Japan, due to historical adoption of technology in manufacturing processes. This market is expected to grow in the APAC region with the highest CAGR of all regions, at 9.7% during the period, with the growth arising due to the growing adoption of emerging technologies such as IoT and AI and an increasing number of connected enterprise activities.

Figure 62 Industrial Automation and Control market outlook to 2027 [40]

The largest market vertical is the Process Automation vertical, making up approximately 60% of the overall market in 2022, with market share predicted to remain unchanged up to 2027, showing the dominance the process industry into the future of this sector, as seen below in **Figure 63**.

Figure 63 Industrial Control and Factory Automation Market, by vertical (USD millions) [40]

Segmentation by solution, **Figure 64**, shows that the largest solution application is predicted to be Distributed Control System (DCS) systems, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 24000 million by 2027, up from a market size of just over USD 17000 million in 2022. All other solutions, while popular and growing, present much smaller growth opportunities, with smaller solutions including Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), Manufacturing Execution System (MES), Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA), Plant Asset Management (PAM) and Industrial Safety based solution systems, as seen in **Figure 64**.

Figure 64 Industrial Control and Factory Automation Market, by solution (USD million) [40]

Segmentation by component, as seen in **Figure 65**, shows that the leading component in Industrial Control and Factory Automation is Industrial Sensors, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 35000 million by 2027, up from a market size of just over USD 21000 million in 2022. Industrial Robots is close behind, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 30000 million by 2027, up from a market size of just over USD 15000 million in 2022. Machine Vision

Systems (USD 17000 million by 2027), Field Instruments (USD 12000 million by 2027) and Process Analysers (USD 7000 million by 2027) all offer potentially beneficial market applications to 2027 [40].

Figure 65 Industrial Control and Factory Automation Market, by component (USD million) [40]

Geographically, growth in this area, as seen in Figure 66, will be led on a total market size and CAGR basis by Asia Pacific, growing to a market of USD 85335 million in 2027 (at a CAGR of 9.7%). Smaller growth rates will be seen in North America, USD 63712 million and CAGR of 7.8%, and Europe USD 47215 million and CAGR of 7% with the Rest of the World making up USD 22539 million and CAGR of 6.1%. Global market size is estimated to grow to USD 218802 million at a CAGR of 8.2% [40].

REGION	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	CAGR
ASIA-PACIFIC	53,746.0	58,437.0	63,790.0	69,926.0	77,086.0	85,335.0	9.7 %
NORTH AMERICA	43,742.0	46,662.0	50,007.0	53,868.0	58,336.0	63,712.0	7.8 %
EUROPE	33,608.0	35,649.0	37,978.0	40,634.0	43,720.0	47,215.0	7 %
REST OF THE WORLD	16,751.0	17,710.0	18,761.0	19,901.0	21,156.0	22,539.0	6.1 %
TOTAL	147,848.0	158,458.0	170,536.0	184,328.0	200,298.0	218,802.0	8.2 %

Figure 66 Industrial Control and Factory Automation Market, by region (CAGR %) [40]

Key commercial leaders in the sector include star actors such as Schneider Electric, Honeywell, Abb, Rockwell, Siemens and Johnson Controls, leading actions in this sector. This companies long established position make them suitable customers or commercial competitors in the sector. There also exist a number of emerging leaders in this area, with companies such as IDEC, SGS Group, Euchner and Velan all acting as potential collaborators, developmental partners or supporters to new innovations in the sector. These Star leaders, Emerging leaders, Participants and Pervasive actors are mapped below in Figure 67.

Figure 67 Industrial Control and Factory Automation Market, Key Actors [40]

The market dynamics of the Industrial Control and Automation Market (Table 7) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 7 Market Dynamics for Industrial Control and Automation Market [40]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergence of connected enterprises • Government initiative to promote industrial automation • Adoption of IoT and AI in industrial environments • Emphasis on optimal utilization of resources and improved efficiency • Increasing integration of machine vision systems with deep learning
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant initial capital investment and subsequent investment for maintenance • Fluctuations in end-use industries • Inability of components to achieve automation solutions • Lack of awareness of benefits
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of industry 4.0 principles for manufacturing • Increased demand for safety compliance automation solutions • Rising need for augmented reality and VR technologies
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of standardisation in industrial communication protocols and interfaces • Lack of skilled workforce to operate industrial automation devices and systems • Rising instances of automated cyberattacks • Less precise systems due to differences between simulations and real life • Complexity in deployment of industrial control and factory automation solutions

8.3. Industry 4.0

The global Industry 4.0 Market has seen steady growth since its inception, with the market evaluated at USD 64.9 billion in 2021. This market is predicted to grow at an average CAGR of 20.6% from 2021, to an estimated market size of US 165.5 billion by 2026 [41], as in Figure 68. The largest region of

interested is predicted to be the Asia-Pacific region, with this growth making up approximately 41% of the global industry 4.0 market in 2021. This growth in the APC region, is attributed to rapid economic growth in the region, the expansion of smart factory installations in the regions manufacturing sector. Increasing demand for industrial robotic systems in the pharmaceutical and medical device manufacturing sectors is a major driver of this growth with new product launches expected to produce lucrative opportunities for actors in the coming years.

Figure 68 Industry 4.0 Market Size 2022 and 2027 [41]

The largest market segment is predicted to be the DT space, with it expected to record the highest CAGR of 61.8% during the period, showing its significant growth potential and value. While this segment shows the largest growth potential, there exists significant additional potential in the other segments, with significant CAGR over 10 predicted by 2026 in the following segments: Industrial Sensors (33.8%), Industrial Robots (33.7%) and Machine Vision (13.4%), with more opportunities found in other segments, as seen in Figure 69.

Source: Annual Reports, Press Releases, Expert Interviews, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 69 Segment growth for Industry 4.0 Market (2021 and 2026) [41]

Geographically, growth in the modular construction sector, as seen in Figure 70, will be led on a total market size basis by Asia Pacific, growing to a market of USD 61300 million in 2026 (at a CAGR of 18%) and on a CAGR basis by North America at a 24% rate (to a market size of USD 49000 million) to 2026. Smaller growth rates will be seen in Europe, USD 42600 million and CAGR of 22.5% to

2026, with the Rest of the World making up USD 12500 million and CAGR of 16.1% to 2026. Global market size is estimated to regional sit at grow to USD 165500 million at a CAGR of 20.6% [41].

REGION	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	CAGR
NORTH AMERICA	16,700.0	19,300.0	22,900.0	28,100.0	36,200.0	49,000.0	24 %
EUROPE	15,500.0	17,700.0	20,700.0	25,100.0	31,900.0	42,600.0	22.5 %
ASIA-PACIFIC	26,800.0	30,500.0	35,300.0	41,200.0	49,400.0	61,300.0	18 %
REST OF THE WORLD	5,900.0	6,500.0	7,200.0	8,400.0	10,000.0	12,500.0	16.1 %
TOTAL	64,900.0	73,900.0	86,100.0	102,800.0	127,500.0	165,500.0	20.6 %

Figure 70 Industry 4.0 Market, by region 2021-2028 (USD million) [41]

Geographically, this growth in Industry 4.0 market will be led by large global economies, as seen in Figure 71, including the US (25.8% CAGR), UK (24.7% CAGR), Germany (22.5% CAGR), France (22% CAGR) and India (21.3%). All other global regions are expected to see market growth from 2021 to 2026, but with CAGRs between 15% and 20% all other regions over that period in Asia, Africa and South America.

Figure 71 Industry 4.0 global predicted market growth rates 2021-2026 [41]

The market dynamics of the Industry 4.0 market (**Table 8**) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 8 Market Dynamics for Industry 4.0 Market [41]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid adoption of AI and IOT in manufacturing sector • Increased demand for industrial robots in pharmaceutical and medical device manufacturing sector • Rising government investments in 3D printing and additive manufacturing • Growing adopting of blockchain technology in manufacturing industry
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of skilled workforce conversant with new developments in AI and IOT sectors • Restricted use of industrial robots in startups due to high implementation costs • High costs if 3D printing materials prevents small companies from competing with big players • Negative health effects of excessive use of AR and VR
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing application of AI and IOT in medical wearables • Rising popularity of 5G in cloud robotics sector • Surge in use of 3D printing technology for medical equipment and customized drugs during covid-19 pandemic
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Susceptibility of IoT and AI technologies to cyberattacks • Interoperability and integration issues of industrial robots • High costs associated with deployment of VR technology.

8.4. Smart Manufacturing/Industry 4.0 Market Impact on the 5G-Timber Project

The overall Smart Manufacturing/Industry 4.0 market will have a significant impact on the 5-Timber project. The adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies, such as IoT, AI, and automation, would enable the project to achieve its goals of increasing efficiency, reducing waste, and improving product quality. By leveraging these technologies, the project could improve its production processes, reduce downtime, and optimize resource utilization.

Additionally, the use of 5G technology would enable real-time communication and data transfer between different stages of the production process, leading to faster decision-making and more agile operations. The integration of Industry 4.0 technologies with 5G would enable the project to achieve the goal of a fully digitized and interconnected production system.

Furthermore, the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies would have a positive impact on the project's target financial improvement goals via reducing costs and increasing revenue. By optimizing production processes, the project outcomes could reduce waste and improve quality, leading to

cost savings and increased customer satisfaction. The use of predictive maintenance, data-driven design, and real-time monitoring would also reduce the risk of equipment failure and increase asset lifespan, leading to further cost savings.

Overall, the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies and 5G communication would enable the 5-Timber project to achieve its goals of sustainable production, improved efficiency, and increased profitability. The project and its impacts would be well-positioned to compete in a rapidly evolving market that demands greater efficiency, quality, and sustainability.

9. 5G-TIMBER Market Potential

This section looks at the UC Categories and UCs therein in order to making the early market potential of each. Overall UCs are described and a PESTEL analysis is conducted for the overall UC.

9.1. Use Case 1 - Data-Driven Sawmill and Woodworking Machine Setup

Overview

UC Cat1 aims to enhance timber production in sawmills using Industry 5.0 technologies. Hekotek and Harmet are responsible for UC Cat1, with Hekotek designing and selling sawmill equipment and Harmet serving as a customer. UC Cat1 will leverage 5G network technologies, DT models, sensorisation, and edge/cloud computing to improve sawn timber handling. Video streams processed by machine vision and AI algorithms will replace the current monitoring system relying on cameras and human operators to increase responsiveness and reliability. Viiratsi and Aegviidu, the two pilot sawmills, may participate to ensure the involvement of all stakeholders in the WVC

PESTEL Analysis

A PESTEL analysis for UC Cat 1 - Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup was completed using a top-down approach, with the process continuously refined and repeated to further gain insights into the problem and market area over the duration of the project. This analysis is outlined below and visualised in Appendix 2.

Political:

- Changes in government regulations and policies related to woodworking and sawmill industry.
- Potential for trade restrictions and tariffs that may impact the cost and availability of raw materials.
- Environmental regulations related to the use of natural resources and waste management.

Economic:

- Fluctuations in the demand for wood products and its impact on the sawmill and woodworking industries.
- Competition from other industries, such as synthetic materials, which may reduce demand for wooden products.
- The availability of capital investment and funding for the implementation of data-driven technologies.

Sociocultural:

- Changing consumer preferences and attitudes towards wood products and sustainability.
- The availability of skilled workers for the operation and maintenance of data-driven sawmills and woodworking machines.
- Cultural attitudes towards the use of technology in traditional industries.

Technological:

- Advancements in data-driven and 5G technologies that may impact the sawmill and woodworking industries.
- Integration of new technologies into existing processes and systems.
- The need for ongoing training and development of skills to keep up with technological advancements.

Legal:

- Compliance with intellectual property laws and regulations related to the use of data-driven technologies.
- Contracts and agreements related to the use of data and intellectual property.
- Liability and risk management related to the use of data-driven sawmills and woodworking machines.

Environmental:

- The impact of sawmill and woodworking operations on the environment, such as deforestation and waste management.
- The potential for data-driven technologies to reduce the environmental impact of the sawmill and woodworking industries.
- Compliance with environmental regulations and sustainability goals.

9.1.1. UC1.1: Data and Material Models Driven Lumber Production and Handling

UC Overview

UC1.1 uses digital wood models and field data to improve decision-making in lumber processing and handling. This is done through data- and material-model-driven production and handling. The aim is to increase yield, improve lumber quality, and reduce scrap and non-conformities by predicting the mechanical behaviour of the material to support cutting decisions and parameters. The wood model is also used to predict the status of lumbers to avoid damage during storage and transportation.

5G Benefits

The advantages of 5G technology include the ability to connect devices and gather information from the field (mMTC). It also addresses the need for improved mobile broadband in rural areas where sawmills often reside. Compared to 4G and 5G NSA, 5G offers improved methods for managing and ensuring service quality (such as slices and E2E quality).

Potential Industry Benefits

The ROI for the stakeholders involved in UC1.1 is listed in **Table 5**, with benefits including increased functionality for sawmill equipment manufacturers, reduced waste and improved quality for sawmill owners, better quality for end users, and the opportunity for RTOs to utilize research results. The proposed approaches are scalable, with potential for embedding digital models of wood and adding other models in the pre-processing of logs to increase sawmill equipment functionality and appeal to customers. The adoption of UC1.1 in the lumber industry can have several potential impacts and benefits, including:

- Increased yield: By using data- and material-model-driven production and handling, the lumber industry can optimize the cutting process to increase yield, resulting in more usable wood and less waste. According to a study by the Forest Products Journal, a 1% increase in lumber yield can result in USD 5 million in additional revenue for a large sawmill [43].
- Improved lumber quality: By predicting the mechanical behaviour of the wood and using this information to support cutting decisions and parameters, the lumber industry can improve the quality of the lumber

produced. This can lead to higher prices for the wood, as higher quality wood is often more valuable.

- **Reduced scrap and non-conformities:** By predicting the status of lumbers and avoiding damage during storage and transportation, the lumber industry can reduce scrap and non-conformities. This can result in cost savings, as well as improved customer satisfaction and reputation.

Overall, the adoption of UC1.1 has the potential to generate significant cost savings and revenue increases for the lumber industry. While exact quantitative predictions may be difficult, studies have shown that even small improvements in yield and quality can result in significant financial benefits.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 72**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Improved efficiency •Better data management •Increased safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •High costs •Technical challenges •Resistance to change
	Weaknesses		
External	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Competitive advantage •Improved decision making •New revenue streams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cybersecurity risks •Dependence on technology •Technical obsolescence
	Threats		

Figure 72 UC1.1. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- **Improved efficiency:** With 5G connectivity, sawmills and woodworking machines can communicate with each other in real-time, allowing for optimized processes and increased productivity.
- **Better data management:** Data-driven machine setups allow for improved data collection, analysis, and reporting, providing valuable insights into the production process.

- Increased safety: With real-time monitoring and control, 5G technology can help prevent accidents and ensure safer working conditions for employees.

Weaknesses include:

- High costs: Implementing 5G technology and data-driven machine setups can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized sawmills and woodworking facilities.
- Technical challenges: Implementing 5G technology and data-driven machine setups requires significant technical expertise, which may be difficult for some sawmills and woodworking facilities to acquire.
- Resistance to change: Some employees may resist adopting new technologies and processes, which can slow down implementation and impact productivity.

Opportunities include :

- Competitive advantage: Implementing 5G and data-driven machine setups can provide sawmills and woodworking facilities with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved decision making: The insights generated from data-driven machine setups can inform better decision making, leading to improved production processes and increased profitability.
- New revenue streams: Data-driven machine setups can open up new revenue streams through the sale of valuable insights to other sawmills and woodworking facilities.

Threats include:

- Cybersecurity risks: 5G technology introduces new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.
- Dependence on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the industry in the long term.
- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the 5G and data-driven machine setups that are implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.

Overall, the application of data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setups in a 5G environment for the timber industry presents both significant opportunities and challenges. Implementing these technologies can bring about significant improvements in efficiency, safety, and profitability, but also requires significant investment and technical expertise, as well as a willingness to adapt to new technologies and processes.

9.1.2. UC1.2: DTs Assisted Assembly, Remote Operation and Servicing for Woodworking Machinery

UC Overview

The objective of UC1.2 is to improve the operation and control of the timber packing machine using a DT and Machine Learning (ML) models. The packing machine is an automatic machine that collects, moves, and packs sawn timbers made by Hekotek and used by customers. The DT and ML models will be used to optimize process parameters, identify and classify anomalous situations that may cause machine stops (such as jams and misalignments), and improve future machine designs. An AR representation of the machine will also be developed to support operator assembly and manual service operations.

5G Benefits

UC1.2 aims to enhance the timber packing machine operation and control with a DT and ML models. The packing machine, which collects, moves and packs sawn timbers made by Hekotek, will benefit from the optimization of process parameters, identification of anomalous situations, and future machine design improvements. An AR representation will also be developed to aid operator assembly and manual service operations.

Potential Industry Benefits

The proposed solution in UC1.2 aims to optimize the setup and ramp-up of equipment, improve safety for the machine operator, and enable online process monitoring for the sawmill owner. It leverages 5G technology and open standards to ensure easy adaptation to different machines and manufacturers. The solution is designed without specific requirements for deployment, and the blueprint for data sharing and guidelines for developing DTs in SMEs can also be applied to other manufacturing domains.

The ROI for stakeholders include optimized setup and ramp-up of equipment for the sawmill equipment manufacturers, improved safety for the machine operator, and reduced downtime through advanced online process monitoring for the sawmill owner. The RTOs will benefit from exploiting DT-based approaches, developing ML algorithms for industrial monitoring, and testing cutting-edge XR applications in real-world industrial environments. The adoption of UC1.2 in the 5G Timber project could have several potential impacts and benefits for the industry, including:

- Increased efficiency and productivity of the timber packing machine, leading to reduced downtime and increased throughput. This could translate into significant cost savings for the company and improved customer satisfaction.
- Improved product quality and consistency, as the DT and ML models can help identify and correct potential issues before they result in defective products. This could lead to increased customer satisfaction and reduced costs associated with product returns and rework.
- Reduced maintenance costs and increased machine lifespan, as the AR representation of the machine can help operators identify and address issues more quickly and accurately, leading to fewer breakdowns and less wear and tear on the machine.

While quantitative predictions are not available at this time, the use of DT and ML models in other industries has demonstrated significant improvements in efficiency, productivity, and quality, suggesting that the adoption of UC1.2 could have similar benefits for the timber industry.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages in the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 71**.

		Helpful	Harmful	
Internal	Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved efficiency Increased safety Enhanced accuracy Reduced costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex implementation High initial investments Reliance on technology Lack of technical expertise 	
	External	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased completeness Expansion into new markets Improved sustainability 	Threats

Figure 73 UC1.2. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Improved efficiency: DT technology allows for real-time monitoring and optimization of machinery, reducing downtime and improving production output.
- Increased safety: Remote operation and servicing of machinery can reduce the risk of accidents and injuries for workers.
- Enhanced accuracy: DT technology enables precise tracking and control of machinery, leading to improved quality and consistency of products.
- Reduced costs: By reducing downtime, improving efficiency, and minimizing human error, DT technology can lower the overall cost of operating machinery.

Weaknesses include:

- Complex implementation: Integrating DT technology into existing machinery systems can be complex and time-consuming.
- High initial investment: The cost of implementing DT technology into machinery systems can be significant.
- Reliance on technology: Remote operation and servicing of machinery requires stable and reliable technology infrastructure, which can be subject to failure or disruption.
- Lack of technical expertise: The DT technology is a relatively new field and there may be a shortage of technical expertise available to support its implementation.

Opportunities include:

- Increased competitiveness: Implementing DT technology can increase competitiveness in the woodworking machinery industry by improving production efficiency and reducing costs.
- Expansion into new markets: DT technology can open up new market opportunities by enabling remote operation and servicing of machinery in remote or challenging locations.
- Improved sustainability: DT technology can help to reduce waste, minimize energy consumption, and improve sustainability in the woodworking machinery industry.

Threats include:

- Technological advancements: As the DT technology evolves and advances, the current technology used for remote operation and servicing of machinery may become obsolete.
- Data security concerns: The use of DT technology raises data security concerns, particularly in industries such as woodworking machinery where sensitive information such as production processes and customer data may be involved.
- Regulatory restrictions: There may be regulatory restrictions on the use of DT technology for remote operation and servicing of machinery in certain countries or regions.
- Competition: The DT technology is becoming increasingly common in the woodworking machinery industry, which may increase competition and reduce the potential for differentiation.

9.1.3. UC1.3: Data and AI Driven Industrial Machines' Fault Prediction and Design Support

UC Overview

UC1.3 implements modern maintenance techniques in small-scale machinery production using IoT data and predictive maintenance for sawmills and woodworking machines over the 5G network. Predictive maintenance aims to minimize unplanned downtime and repair costs and extend asset life. Machine data is accessible to customers and manufacturers for maintenance analytics and guidelines, promoting an eco-friendly, paperless approach.

5G Benefits

The machine's monitoring equipment must operate on battery power. 5G technology advancements, including enhanced Machine-Time Communication (eMTC) and NB-IoT integration, will extend battery life. The monitoring equipment, with a 5 Wh battery capacity, is expected to last up to 10-15 years, surpassing the maximum 10-year battery life of previous LTE technologies.

Potential Industry Benefits

The proposed solution for UC1.3 will aim to improve overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) for sawmill equipment manufacturers and sawmill owners, as well as provide more effective and smart maintenance approaches. Additionally, the solution will involve the development of 5G-enabled sensors by RTOs and the application of AI-based predictive maintenance on real-world case studies. The solution will rely on wireless technologies and eliminate the need for complex routing during the setup and installation of monitoring sensors, making it more accessible and cost-effective. The potential industry impacts and benefits of UC1.3 adoption in the 5G Timber project include:

- Reduced maintenance costs: Predictive maintenance can reduce the costs of unplanned downtime and repair, leading to significant cost savings for sawmills and woodworking manufacturers.
- Increased equipment uptime: Predictive maintenance can also increase equipment uptime, allowing sawmills and woodworking manufacturers to produce more output, leading to increased revenue.
- Improved asset lifespan: By identifying potential issues before they become major problems, predictive maintenance can extend the lifespan of equipment, leading to cost savings and increased return on investment.
- Eco-friendly approach: The use of IoT data and predictive maintenance promotes an eco-friendly, paperless approach to maintenance, reducing waste and promoting sustainability.

Quantitative predictions are difficult to provide at present, as the impact of UC1.3 adoption will vary depending on the specific sawmill or woodworking manufacturer, evidenced via trials. However, studies have shown that predictive maintenance can reduce maintenance costs by up to 30%, and increase equipment uptime by up to 20% [44].

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 74**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved machine performance • Reduced maintenance costs • Improved design support 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical challenges • High costs • Resistance to change 	
External	<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive advantages • Improved decision making • New revenue streams 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity risks • Dependence on technology • Technical obsolescence 	

Figure 74 UC1.3. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- **Improved machine performance:** By using data and AI to predict machine faults, industrial facilities can take proactive measures to prevent downtime and improve overall machine performance.
- **Reduced maintenance costs:** Predictive maintenance can help facilities identify and address machine faults before they escalate, reducing the need for costly repairs and unplanned downtime.
- **Improved design support:** Data and AI can be used to analyze machine performance and identify areas for improvement, leading to the design of more efficient and reliable machines.

Weaknesses include:

- **Technical challenges:** Implementing AI and data-driven machine fault prediction and design support requires significant technical expertise, which may be difficult for some industrial facilities to acquire.
- **High costs:** Implementing AI and data-driven solutions can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized industrial facilities.

- Resistance to change: Some employees may resist adopting new technologies and processes, which can slow down implementation and impact productivity.

Opportunities include:

- Competitive advantage: Implementing AI and data-driven machine fault prediction and design support can provide industrial facilities with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved decision making: The insights generated from machine fault prediction and design support can inform better decision making, leading to improved production processes and increased profitability.
- New revenue streams: AI and data-driven machine fault prediction and design support can open up new revenue streams through the sale of valuable insights to other industrial facilities.

Threats include:

- Cybersecurity risks: AI and data-driven solutions introduce new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.
- Dependence on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the industry in the long term.
- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the AI and data-driven solutions implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.

9.2. Use Case 2 – Modular Wood House Factory

Overview

UC Cat2 aims to integrate various technologies in a real-world setting, focusing on the manufacturing process for wooden house modules at Harmet's factory in Estonia. This use case explores the integration of a private 5G network to support multiple applications and tools. The current assembly process is divided into 2D and 3D phases, which can lead to errors due to discrepancies between designs and technical drawings. There is also no system to track people and materials on the factory floor, resulting in inefficiencies and security issues. Three sub-use cases (UC2.1, UC2.2, and UC2.3) will implement a 5G-based tracking system, provide 3D data to

operators through a VR interface, and establish a feedback mechanism from the production floor to the design department using DTs.

PESTEL Analysis

A PESTEL analysis for UC Cat2- Modular wood house factory was completed using a top-down approach, with the process continuously refined and repeated to further gain insights into the problem and market area over the duration of the project. This analysis is outlined below and visualised in Appendix 2.

Political:

- Government policies and regulations surrounding the implementation and use of 5G technology in the manufacturing industry
- Data privacy and security concerns regarding the use of 5G technology in the factory
- Competition from other industries and factories who are also incorporating 5G technology
- Availability of government funding for the implementation of 5G technology in the factory

Economic:

- Costs associated with the implementation and maintenance of 5G technology in the factory
- Potential for increased efficiency and productivity resulting in higher profits
- Market demand for modular wood houses and the impact it has on the factory's financial stability
- The effect of economic downturns on the factory's ability to afford and maintain 5G technology

Sociocultural:

- Acceptance of 5G technology by the factory's workforce and the general public
- Employee training and education required for the effective use of 5G technology
- The impact of 5G technology on the environment and sustainability
- The role of the factory in the wider community and how the implementation of 5G technology may affect it

Technological:

- The availability and reliability of 5G technology and infrastructure
- The compatibility of the factory's current technology with 5G
- Advancements in technology that may disrupt or improve the use of 5G in the factory
- The potential for 5G technology to improve or disrupt the manufacturing process of modular wood houses

Legal:

- Compliance with relevant laws and regulations surrounding the use of 5G technology
- Intellectual property concerns regarding the use of 5G technology in the factory
- Liability issues regarding the use of 5G technology in the factory
- Contractual agreements between the factory and 5G technology providers

Environmental:

- Energy efficiency and reduction of waste in the factory through the implementation of 5G technology
- The impact of 5G technology on the environment, including electromagnetic pollution and carbon footprint
- The use of 5G technology in environmentally friendly processes, such as sustainable sourcing of materials
- The responsibility of the factory to adhere to environmental regulations and guidelines regarding the use of 5G technology.

9.2.1. UC2.1: Precise Localisation for Production Processes Optimization and Human Safety

UC Overview

UC2.1 aims to demonstrate the benefits of utilizing 5G technology for indoor localization of materials and human operators in a manufacturing facility, improving logistics and safety. 5G technology offers promising results for precise localization with a focus on 20-30 cm accuracy in specific deployments. The project will examine various techniques to enhance efficiency and safety while complying with GDPR regulations, and the results will also be used to improve production processes in UC2.2.

5G Benefits

Adopting 5G technology brings several advantages, particularly with regards to localization services (LCS). Additionally, the ability to manage a large number of locatable items (such as people, tools, or parts) through Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) is also improved. Finally, 5G technology provides the capability of low-power devices, making it possible to maintain long-lasting localization without the need for frequent battery recharge.

Potential Industry Benefits

Woodhouse Manufacturers will benefit from improved assembly scheduling capability and workers will have improved safety in the workplace. 5G module manufacturers will implement the latest 5G release, while RTO will develop a new 5G-based localization algorithm. The solution is based on 5G radios and its scalability within the factory will depend on the number of radios and computing capability available. However, the cost of each 5G radio will be the main critical factor for extending the approach beyond the case study. The proposed solution will use general-purpose hardware as much as possible for scalability to other facilities and the manufacturing domain in general.

The adoption of 5G technology for indoor localization in manufacturing facilities can have several potential industry impacts and benefits, including:

- Improved efficiency: Precise localization of materials and human operators can optimize production processes, reducing the time and cost required to complete tasks. For instance, the reduction of search times for misplaced or lost items can lead to increased productivity.
- Enhanced safety: 5G-enabled indoor localization can help prevent accidents in manufacturing facilities by ensuring that workers and materials are in the correct locations. This can also help reduce the risk of injuries and property damage.
- Better data collection: 5G technology can provide real-time data on the location of materials and workers, enabling more accurate inventory management and production planning. This can help optimize supply chain management and improve decision-making processes.

Quantitative predictions are difficult to provide, as the impact of UC2.1 will depend on various factors, including the size and complexity of the manufacturing facility and the specific deployment of 5G technology.

However, studies have shown that improving efficiency and safety in manufacturing facilities can result in significant cost savings and increased revenue. For example, a report by the US National Safety Council estimated that workplace injuries and illnesses cost US businesses USD 171 billion in 2019 [45]. By implementing 5G-enabled indoor localization, manufacturing facilities may be able to reduce the incidence of workplace accidents, resulting in cost savings and increased productivity.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 75**.

		Helpful	Harmful
		Internal	External
Internal	Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved accuracy Increased efficiency Reduced downtime 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High costs Technical challenges Data privacy concerns 	
	Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved safety Competitive advantage Improved decision making 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technological obsolescence Cybersecurity risks Reliance on technology 	

Figure 75 UC2.1. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Improved accuracy: Precise localisation technology can provide highly accurate data, enabling optimization of production processes and ensuring human safety.
- Increased efficiency: By providing real-time information about the location and movement of workers and machinery, localisation technology can help streamline processes and improve efficiency.
- Reduced downtime: With real-time monitoring of machinery and worker movements, potential issues can be detected and addressed before they cause significant downtime.

Weaknesses include:

- High costs: Implementing localisation technology can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized factories.
- Technical challenges: Implementing localisation technology requires significant technical expertise, which may be difficult for some factories to acquire.
- Data privacy concerns: The collection and storage of data related to worker movements and machinery location may raise concerns about privacy and data security.

Opportunities include:

- Improved safety: Precise localisation technology can help improve worker safety by providing real-time information about worker movements and machinery locations, reducing the risk of accidents.
- Competitive advantage: Implementing localisation technology can provide factories with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved decision making: The data generated by localisation technology can inform better decision making, leading to improved production processes and increased profitability.

Threats include:

- Technological obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the localisation technology that is implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.
- Cybersecurity risks: The use of technology introduces new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.
- Reliance on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the factory in the long term.

9.2.2. UC2.2: DT, AR and Industry 5.0 UX Assisted Production Supported by ZSM 5G Data Exchange

UC Overview

UC2.2 uses AR and Industry 5.0 to improve wood-house assembly quality, efficiency, and safety at Harmet's factory. A DT of the product and production

system will be created using 5G network capabilities to provide real-time data and optimal solutions for the "3D assembly" phase.

5G Benefits

The advantages of utilizing 5G technology are apparent when considering the technical requirements and the scenario in question. Specifically, for XR applications, 5G networks can deliver a latency of less than 1 millisecond, allowing for adequate computational resources to be dedicated to other elements such as user motion and changes in the environment. Additionally, the combination of eMBB and URLLC applications enable the implementation of a hybrid architecture.

Current devices used for XR, such as HMDs or tablets, may provide sufficient rendering capabilities, but can be uncomfortable to wear, impacting their widespread adoption in industry. With 5G networks, concepts like remote rendering and providing high-quality, interactive 3D content can become a reality. The 5G network also offers improved performance, making it possible to stream high-quality 3D content while maintaining a smooth data flow for visualization purposes. The higher peak rate of 5G compared to other mobile technologies further allows for seamless data exchange with DTs.

Potential Industry Benefits

Woodhouse Manufacturers will benefit from a shorter element assembly time, reduced assembly errors, automated feedback of design errors to BIM models, and a reduction in new workers training time. The 5G module manufacturer will provide 5G connectivity to XR devices, while the 5G provider will test the performance of 5G when streaming XR content. RTOs will focus on developing methodologies and approaches for creating DTs. The proposed solutions will utilize commercial devices and open standards such as OpenXR and will aim to integrate with current IT tools, following ISO standards or ensuring interoperability when no standard is found. Scalability will depend on the availability of modern IT tools and the critical factors include the number of users accessing the tools, cost of devices, and network data rate.

The adoption of UC2.2 can have several potential industry impacts and benefits. By utilizing AR and Industry 5.0 to improve wood-house assembly quality, efficiency, and safety, Harmet can achieve faster and more accurate

assembly, reduce errors and waste, and improve overall productivity. The use of a DT of the product and production system, coupled with real-time data and optimal solutions provided by 5G network capabilities, can further enhance assembly quality and speed while reducing costs.

Quantitative predictions for the benefits of UC2.2 adoption are difficult to provide without more specific results arising from project testing and implementation on Harmet's assembly process. However, it is reasonable to assume that improved efficiency, reduced errors and waste, and enhanced productivity can lead to cost savings and increased revenue for Harmet. Additionally, the use of AR and Industry 5.0 can improve the overall quality of Harmet's products, leading to increased customer satisfaction and potentially greater market share.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 76**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency • Enhanced user experience • Improved collaborations • Predictive maintenance 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs • Technical challenges • Resistance to change 	
External	<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive advantages • Improved decision making • New revenue streams 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity risks • Dependence on technology • Technical obsolescence • Interoperability challenges 	

Figure 76 UC2.2. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Increased efficiency: The use of DTs, AR, and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production can improve the overall efficiency of production processes.

- Enhanced user experience: The use of AR and Industry 5.0 UX technologies can provide workers with a more intuitive and interactive experience, improving their ability to carry out tasks and make decisions.
- Improved collaboration: ZSM 5G data exchange can facilitate real-time communication and collaboration between workers, improving the flow of information and reducing the potential for errors.
- Predictive maintenance: With the ability to gather and analyse large amounts of data, DTs can be used to predict and prevent equipment failures, reducing downtime and maintenance costs.

Weaknesses include:

- High costs: Implementing DTs, AR, and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production, as well as ZSM 5G data exchange, can be expensive, particularly for smaller wood modular house factories.
- Technical challenges: Implementing these technologies requires significant technical expertise, which may be difficult for some factories to acquire.
- Resistance to change: Some workers may resist adopting new technologies and processes, which can slow down implementation and impact productivity.

Opportunities include :

- Competitive advantage: Implementing these technologies can provide wood modular house factories with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved decision making: The insights generated from DTs can inform better decision making, leading to improved production processes and increased profitability.
- New revenue streams: By leveraging their expertise in these technologies, wood modular house factories can open up new revenue streams through the sale of valuable insights to other factories.

Threats include:

- Cybersecurity risks: ZSM 5G data exchange introduces new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.

- Dependence on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the factory in the long term.
- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the DTs, AR, and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production systems that are implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.
- Interoperability challenges: Ensuring compatibility and interoperability between different technologies and systems may be challenging, particularly in a complex and rapidly evolving technological landscape.

Overall, the use of DTs, AR, and Industry 5.0 UX assisted production supported by ZSM 5G data exchange presents both significant opportunities and challenges for wood modular house factories. Implementing these technologies can bring about significant improvements in efficiency, user experience, and profitability, but also requires significant investment and technical expertise, as well as a willingness to adapt to new technologies and processes.

9.2.3. UC2.3: Data Driven Design to Production Cycle Optimisation

UC Overview

UC aims to reduce the time between design and production and provide automated feedback on deviations from the original design. Currently, there's no closed-loop system between design and manufacturing at Harmet, leading to potential problems. By collecting real-time data and categorizing it accurately in the PLM tool, a data-driven design can be achieved, enabling quick identification and resolution of issues.

5G Benefits

The 5G connectivity can bring similar benefits to the tools and applications in this UC as it did in UC2.2, given that the technical requirements are nearly identical. This network will offer the anticipated performance, including low latency, high peak data rate, and dependability, to support the data streams required for XR tools and the connection to the PLM.

Potential Industry Benefits

UC2.3 aims to improve the efficiency and reduce errors in the assembly process of wood houses/buildings by shortening the element assembly time, reducing customer non-compliances, and providing automated feedback of design errors to BIM models. The wood house/building owners will benefit from a reduction in non-compliances. RTOs will benefit from methodologies and approaches to deal with DTs in an industrial environment. The proposed solutions will leverage commercial devices and open standards and will be integrated with current IT tools. The scalability of the solution will be limited to the availability of modern IT tools and the number of users accessing the tools simultaneously, the cost of devices, and the network data rate.

The adoption of Data Driven Design to Production Cycle Optimisation can have several potential industry impacts and benefits, including,

- Reduced design-to-production cycle time, resulting in increased efficiency and faster time-to-market for Harmet's wood products.
- Minimized production errors and deviations from original designs through real-time data collection and categorization.
- Improved product quality and customer satisfaction by quickly identifying and resolving issues.
- Cost savings due to reduced waste and rework resulting from improved production accuracy.
- Increased competitiveness in the marketplace through the adoption of modern, data-driven manufacturing practices.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 77**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Internal	Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved efficiency More accurate designs Great flexibility 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical challenges High costs Data quality issues
	External	Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competitive advantages New Revenue streams Improved decision making 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cybersecurity Risks Dependence on technology Technical obsolescence Data privacy and protection

Figure 77 UC 2.3 SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Improved efficiency: Data-driven design to production cycle optimization can help streamline production processes and increase efficiency, leading to higher productivity and cost savings.
- More accurate design: By using data and AI to inform the design process, designers can make more accurate decisions and produce better designs that consider real-world conditions and constraints.
- Greater flexibility: Data-driven design to production cycle optimization can allow for greater flexibility in production processes, allowing for quicker and more efficient response to changes in customer demand.

Weaknesses include:

- Technical challenges: Implementing data-driven design to production cycle optimization requires significant technical expertise and resources, which may be difficult for some organizations to acquire.
- High costs: Implementing data-driven design to production cycle optimization can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized organizations.
- Data quality issues: The quality of the data used to inform the design process is critical, but collecting and maintaining accurate data can be challenging.

Opportunities include:

- Competitive advantage: Implementing data-driven design to production cycle optimization can provide organizations with a

competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.

- New revenue streams: Data-driven design to production cycle optimization can open up new revenue streams through the sale of valuable insights and improved design solutions to other organizations.
- Improved decision making: The insights generated from data-driven design to production cycle optimization can inform better decision making, leading to improved production processes and increased profitability.

Threats include:

- Cybersecurity risks: The use of data and AI in the design process introduces new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.
- Dependence on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the production process in the long term.
- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the data-driven design to production cycle optimization technologies that are implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.
- Data privacy and protection: The use of sensitive data in the design process raises concerns about data privacy and protection, which must be addressed to ensure compliance with regulations and the trust of customers and stakeholders.

Overall, the implementation of data-driven design to production cycle optimization presents both significant opportunities and challenges. By leveraging data and AI to inform the design process, organizations can improve efficiency, flexibility, and decision making, but also need to invest in the necessary technical resources and address potential risks.

9.3. Use Case 3 – Construction and Renovation with Wooden Elements, Valorisation of Composite Waste

Overview

UC Cat3 covers the lifespan of wooden components. UC3.1 focuses on construction, while UC3.2 examines usage and 5G IoT tools for monitoring

and maintenance. UC3.3 explores alternative composite materials to enhance waste recycling during production.

PESTEL Analysis

A PESTEL analysis for UC Cat3- Construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste was completed using a top-down approach, with the process continuously refined and repeated to further gain insights into the problem and market area over the duration of the project. This analysis is outlined below and visualised in Appendix 2.

Political:

- Government regulations and policies on building materials and waste management can have a significant impact on the use of wooden elements and recycling of composite waste in construction and renovation projects.
- International trade agreements and tariffs can affect the availability and cost of wood and composite materials.

Economic:

- The overall economic situation, including economic growth, inflation, and consumer spending, can impact the demand for construction and renovation projects, as well as the cost of raw materials and labour.
- The availability and cost of funding for research and development in the area of wooden construction and composite waste recycling can also be a factor.

Sociocultural:

- Consumer preferences and attitudes towards sustainability and environmental responsibility can drive demand for environmentally friendly construction and renovation methods, including the use of wooden elements and recycling of composite waste.
- Changing demographics and global population growth can affect demand for housing and construction.

Technological:

- Advances in technology and research in the areas of wooden construction and composite waste recycling can drive the

development of new and improved products and processes, improving efficiency and sustainability.

- The availability and use of digital technologies, such as building information modelling (BIM) and the Internet of Things (IoT), can also impact the construction and renovation process.

Legal:

- Regulations and standards for construction and waste management can have a significant impact on the use of wooden elements and recycling of composite waste.
- Patent laws and intellectual property rights can impact the development and use of new technologies in the area of wooden construction and composite waste recycling.

Environmental:

- Climate change and environmental sustainability concerns are driving a shift towards more environmentally friendly construction and renovation methods, including the use of wooden elements and recycling of composite waste.
- Availability of raw materials and resources, such as wood and recycled materials, can impact the construction and renovation industry.

9.3.1. UC3.1: AR and Industry 5.0 UX Assisted Assembly and Renovation of Green Buildings

UC Overview

UC3.1 aims to validate XR technology in the assembly process of wooden houses on real construction sites using 5G communication technology. A mock-up site will also be used to prototype modular wooden houses and compare the performance of public and private 5G networks. The study will investigate the impact of XR technology on worker safety and comfort, with the participation of Harmet's personnel.

5G Benefits

One of the main advantages of 5G technology is its ability to deliver large amounts of data at a high speed, with a target of 100 Mbps for enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), and low latency of 10ms for Ultra-Reliable and Low

Latency Communications (URLLC). These features are critical for the effective utilization of Extended Reality (XR) devices.

Potential Industry Benefits

In UC3.1, Woodhouse manufacturers will benefit from a shorter building time, fewer assembly errors, and less spare materials at the construction site. Woodhouse owners will have fewer nonconformities, less inspections, and full traceability of components. RTOs will benefit from the exploitation of BIM/DT environments. The proposed solutions will leverage commercial devices and open standards for implementation and will be designed for integration with current IT tools, ensuring interoperability. The scalability of the solution towards other industries is limited only by the availability of modern IT tools, while the scalability in terms of number of users, cost of devices and network data rate will be the critical factors.

Potential industry impacts and benefits of UC3.1 adoption include:

- Improved safety: XR technology can provide workers with a safer working environment by visualizing potential hazards, allowing them to identify and address safety issues before they arise. The use of 5G communication technology can also ensure reliable and low-latency communication in real-time, enabling quick responses to safety concerns.
- Increased efficiency: By using XR technology, workers can visualize the final product before it is built, enabling them to identify and address any design issues before the construction process begins. This can reduce the need for rework and improve the overall efficiency of the construction process.
- Cost savings: The use of XR technology can help to reduce material waste and rework, resulting in cost savings for construction companies. Additionally, the use of 5G communication technology can reduce the need for costly on-site infrastructure, such as wired networks.
- Improved customer satisfaction: By using XR technology, customers can visualize the final product before it is built, providing them with a better understanding of the design and allowing them to make more informed decisions. This can improve customer satisfaction and potentially lead to repeat business.

The specific benefits of UC3.1 adoption will depend on various factors, such as the size of the construction project, the complexity of the design, and the efficiency of the construction process.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 78**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Internal	Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved efficiency Reduced errors Improved safety 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost Technical challenges Resistance to change
	External	Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competitive advantages Improved quality New revenue streams 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical obsolescence Limited access to technology Cybersecurity Risks

Figure 78 UC3.1. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Improved efficiency: With AR and Industry 5.0 UX-assisted assembly, workers can access real-time information and guidance, reducing the time and effort required to complete complex tasks and increasing overall efficiency.
- Reduced errors: AR technology can provide visual cues and instructions, reducing the likelihood of errors and rework during the assembly process.
- Improved safety: Workers can access information and guidance without having to physically access hazardous areas, reducing the risk of accidents and improving safety on the worksite.

Weaknesses include:

- Cost: Implementing AR and Industry 5.0 UX-assisted assembly can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized construction companies.
- Technical challenges: AR technology requires significant technical expertise to set up and maintain, which may be difficult for some construction companies to acquire.
- Resistance to change: Some workers may resist adopting new technologies, which can slow down implementation and impact productivity.

Opportunities include:

- Competitive advantage: Implementing AR and Industry 5.0 UX-assisted assembly can provide construction companies with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved quality: AR technology can help ensure that the assembly process is completed correctly, leading to improved quality in the final product.
- New revenue streams: AR technology can open up new revenue streams through the sale of services and expertise to other construction companies.

Threats include:

- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that AR technology may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.
- Limited access to technology: Some workers may not have access to the technology required to use AR-assisted assembly, which could limit its adoption.
- Cybersecurity risks: AR technology introduces new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.

9.3.2. UC3.2: Long Term SHM of Wooden Construction Using IoT and Embedded AI

UC Overview

UC3.2 aims to monitor the structural health of wooden constructions throughout their lifecycle using 5G-based IoT devices connected through a

commercial 5G network. Moisture damage during storage periods will be given special attention. The feasibility of incorporating 5G connectivity into the modules will also be explored.

5G Benefits

The prime benefit of utilizing 5G technologies lies in the resource optimization of 5G IoT sensors to keep track of the wooden house modules, from their completion to the setup on the construction site. Additionally, 5G zero-touch configuration capabilities provide automatic setup of 5G connectivity and monitoring systems, thus eliminating the need for manual network element configuration and reducing the overall cost of installing connectivity in the wooden modules over time.

Potential Industry Benefits

In UC3.2, stakeholders such as Woodhouse Manufacturers, Woodhouse Owners and RTO and Academics can expect benefits such as monitoring the lifecycle of the woodhouse, improving design with data, implementing predictive/preventive maintenance, using embedded 5G capabilities, and having digital wood models and building maintenance algorithms. These approaches can be extended to monitoring more variables and have low energy consumption, leading to possible extensive adoption in building management. Potential industry impacts and benefits of UC3.2 adoption may include:

- Improved safety: By continuously monitoring the structural health of wooden constructions, potential risks and hazards can be detected and addressed in real-time, enhancing overall safety.
- Increased lifespan of structures: Early detection of moisture damage or other structural issues through continuous monitoring can prevent further damage and help prolong the lifespan of wooden structures.
- Cost savings: Timely maintenance and repair of wooden constructions can save costs associated with more extensive repairs or replacements that may be necessary if damage goes undetected.
- Environmental sustainability: IoT-enabled monitoring of wooden constructions can promote more sustainable practices by reducing waste and minimizing the environmental impact associated with repairs or replacements.

Future quantitative predictions for the benefits of UC3.2 adoption depend on various factors such as the size and scale of the implementation, the cost

savings associated with early detection, and the impact on the lifespan of chosen wooden constructions.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 79**.

		Helpful	Harmful
		Internal	<p style="text-align: center;">Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Safety • Increase efficiency • Improved decision making
External	<p style="text-align: center;">Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive advantages • Improve sustainability • New revenue streams 	<p style="text-align: center;">Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity risks • Dependence on technology • Technical obsolescence • Data privacy 	

Figure 79 UC3.2. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Improved safety: By continuously monitoring the structural health of wooden construction modules, potential issues can be detected and addressed in a timely manner, reducing the risk of accidents and failure.
- Increased efficiency: Automated monitoring and analysis of structural health data using IoT, and embedded AI can provide real-time insights into the performance of the modules, leading to improved processes and increased productivity.
- Improved decision-making: Data collected from the IoT and embedded AI systems can inform better decision-making and maintenance planning, leading to reduced costs and increased profitability.

Weaknesses include:

- High costs: Implementing IoT and embedded AI systems for long-term structural health monitoring can be expensive, particularly for small- to medium-sized green building organizations.

- Technical challenges: Implementing IoT and embedded AI systems requires significant technical expertise, which may be difficult for some organizations to acquire.
- Resistance to change: Some employees may resist adopting new technologies and processes, which can slow down implementation and impact productivity.

Opportunities include :

- Competitive advantage: Implementing IoT and embedded AI systems for long-term structural health monitoring can provide green building organizations with a competitive advantage over those that have not adopted these technologies.
- Improved sustainability: By continuously monitoring the structural health of the modules, organizations can ensure that the modules are functioning at their optimal level, reducing energy consumption and increasing the lifespan of the structures.
- New revenue streams: The insights generated from the IoT and embedded AI systems can open up new revenue streams through the sale of valuable insights to other green building organizations.

Threats include:

- Cybersecurity risks: IoT and embedded AI systems introduce new cybersecurity risks that must be addressed to protect against potential cyber-attacks.
- Dependence on technology: Over-reliance on technology can result in reduced human decision-making and problem-solving skills, which could impact the industry in the long term.
- Technical obsolescence: The rapid pace of technological change means that the IoT and embedded AI systems implemented today may quickly become outdated, requiring ongoing investment to stay current.
- Data privacy: The collection and storage of sensitive data about the structural health of green buildings can pose privacy concerns and raise questions about who has access to this data.

Overall, the implementation of long-term structural health monitoring of wooden construction modules using IoT and embedded AI presents both significant opportunities and challenges. Implementing these technologies can bring about significant improvements in safety, efficiency, and

profitability, but also requires significant investment and technical expertise, as well as a willingness to adapt to new technologies and processes.

9.3.3. UC3.3: Wooden Composites Waste Recycling

UC Overview

The aim of UC3.3 is to assess the viability of the models that are used to make decisions on the right kind of wood-based materials, such as Oriented Strand Board, solid wood products, and engineered wood products, to be used in the manufacturing and design of wooden houses. The ultimate objective is to enhance waste recycling during the production process.

5G Benefits

The health monitoring sensors mentioned in UC 2.3 can also be utilized for predicting waste. By leveraging the existing setup, the data gathered from the moisture and geometry readings can be used to refine the model and determine the health status of the wood.

Potential Industry Benefits

The woodhouse manufacturers aim to reduce waste from wood composites, improve and simplify their recycling process, and accurately report waste amounts. On the other hand, RTO and academics aim to validate LCA models and circularity indicators for wooden composites, as well as predict their recyclability. These approaches and analyses in the construction sector can be applied to other industries with similar wooden composites. Potential industry impacts and benefits from the adoption of UC3.3 in the 5G Timber project include:

- Environmental benefits: By enhancing waste recycling during the production process, UC3.3 can reduce the environmental impact of wooden construction and increase the sustainability of the industry.
- Cost savings: By optimizing the selection of wood-based materials, UC3.3 can lead to cost savings in the production process.
- Improved product quality: By selecting the right kind of wood-based materials, UC3.3 can improve the quality of wooden houses, which can lead to increased customer satisfaction and brand reputation.

By reducing waste and optimizing material selection, UC3.3 can potentially lead to significant cost savings and environmental benefits.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT Analysis for this UC was completed using a top-down approach, and will be further evolved throughout the duration of the project. This analysis will help position the proposed solution into its target market, support in identifying potential opportunities and advantages into the future. This analysis can be seen below in **Figure 80**.

		Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Internal	Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Benefits • Cost Savings • New Product Opportunities • Increase Sustainability 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of infrastructure • Low demand for recycled component • High Processing costs • Quality Concerns
		External	External

Figure 80 UC3.3. SWOT Analysis

Strengths include:

- Environmental benefits: Recycling wooden composites helps reduce waste and minimize the impact on the environment by conserving resources and reducing emissions.
- Cost savings: Recycling wooden composites can be a more cost-effective solution than disposing of waste or using raw materials, as it can reduce the need to purchase new resources.
- New product opportunities: Recycling wooden composites can create new product opportunities by upcycling waste materials into new products.
- Increased sustainability: Recycling wooden composites can contribute to increased sustainability, which is becoming increasingly important for businesses and consumers.

Weaknesses include:

- Lack of infrastructure: In some areas, there may be a lack of infrastructure for the collection and processing of recycled wooden composites, making it difficult to implement recycling programs.

- Low demand for recycled materials: There may be limited demand for recycled wooden composites, which can reduce the feasibility of recycling programs.
- High processing costs: The processing costs of recycled wooden composites can be high, making it difficult for businesses to implement recycling programs.
- Quality concerns: There may be concerns about the quality of recycled wooden composites compared to new materials, which can impact their acceptability and marketability.

Opportunities include:

- Growing awareness of sustainability: The growing awareness of sustainability is creating increased demand for recycled products and materials, including recycled wooden composites.
- Increasing regulations: Increasing regulations on waste management and environmental sustainability are creating new opportunities for businesses to implement recycling programs.
- Innovations in recycling technology: Innovations in recycling technology are making it easier and more cost-effective to recycle wooden composites, providing new opportunities for businesses.
- Market expansion: As recycling programs become more widespread, there may be new opportunities to expand the market for recycled wooden composites.

Threats include:

- Competition from other materials: Recycled wooden composites may face competition from other materials, such as plastic composites or metals, which can reduce their market share.
- Fluctuations in raw material prices: Fluctuations in raw material prices can impact the economics of recycling wooden composites, making it less feasible in some cases.
- Economic downturns: Economic downturns can reduce demand for recycled materials, including recycled wooden composites, making it difficult for businesses to implement recycling programs.
- Lack of consumer awareness: There may be a lack of consumer awareness about the benefits of recycled wooden composites, which can reduce demand and limit market growth.

10. Conclusions

This document outlined the initial market analysis and technology monitoring for the 5G-TIMBER project, and its focus areas, during the first 9 months of the project. It started by describing related project goals, the features of 5G technologies and the potential use cases that can be implemented under the remit of this project. It also explored the political factors surrounding the implementation of 5G and how they impact the adoption of the technology.

The document provided a comprehensive overview of relevant market sectors and key areas that involved in the 5G technology ecosystem, with particular emphasis of the areas of impact under that forestry and timber goals of this project, namely, Wood Industry, Wood Materials, Sawn wood, Wood Energy, Composite Wood Materials, Wood Based Panels, Modular Construction Markets, Construction Technology Markets, and Smart Manufacturing. Key market findings related to the 5G-Timber project include

- The global market for timber and wood products is expected to continue to grow in the coming years, with driven by an increasing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly materials and the growth of the construction industry, furniture, and paper industries, among others.
- The timber industry is facing several challenges, including the shortage of raw materials, labour shortages, and environmental concerns. The adoption of 5G technology and related solutions can help address these challenges and create new opportunities for the industry.
- The adoption of 5G technology in the timber industry has the potential to significantly improve productivity, reduce costs, and enhance safety, leading to a more efficient and sustainable supply chain.
- Specific use cases of 5G technology in the timber industry, such as those explored in the 5G Timber project, can have a measurable impact on key performance indicators such as machine downtime, energy usage, and quality control.
- The use of 5G technology in the timber industry also presents new opportunities for innovation, such as the development of DTs, ML models, and AR applications.
- Other emerging trends in the industry include the use of advanced analytics and automation technologies, such as robotics and AI, and the

adoption of circular economy models that promote resource efficiency and waste reduction.

- The adoption of 5G technology in the timber industry can also have broader economic and environmental benefits, such as reducing waste and improving resource efficiency, as well as supporting the transition to a circular economy.
- The 5G Timber project and related initiatives highlight the potential for technology to drive innovation and transformation in the timber industry, enabling it to become more efficient, sustainable, and competitive in the global market.

The document delved into the 3 core UC categories of the project: Data-driven sawmill and woodworking machine setup, Modular wood-house factory and Construction and renovation with wooden elements and valorisation of composite waste. For each of these areas, the document provided a high-level overview and an early analysis of the role of 5G technology through the use of UC Categories PESTEL and UCs SWOT analyses. The analysis also included indications of the initial benefits imparted by 5G to the developed UCs along with some early thoughts on the potential industry related benefits derived for key actors.

The next steps include further ongoing monitoring and updating of technology and market related aspects, a focus on customer validation actions and solution alignment, and the work towards the creation of a viable commercial exploitation plan leading to deliverable D5.2.

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12. Appendix I

Additional market relevant data and information.

Lidar

Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) is a remote sensing method that gathers “points” (3D coordinates) from the earth’s surface using laser light pulses. LIDAR, often also known as 3D scanning, collects millions of these points together and create a point cloud. A digital 3D model or a DT of the scanned environment can be created on the basis of this point cloud. In the construction sector such exact digital representation helps in planning and analysing - either the landscape or renovation project of an existing building. In 2021 the value of the LIDAR global market size was USD 1.8 billion. It is predicted to grow from 2022 to 2030 annually by 9.6%. On a European level, the Lidar market was estimated to be worth USD 435.3 million in 2021, with a future predicted CAGR of 7.5% form 2022 – 2030, as seen in **Figure 81**. The growth of the market is connected to the technologically advanced LIDAR solutions which will save manhours. Rising interest for 3D visualization in sectors such as civil engineering, military and defence, topographical surveys and corridor mapping are the main factors behind the expected growth of the market by 2030. The biggest challenges to the market growth are the lack of educated customers, the high cost of LIDAR services and narrow availability of geospatial data.

Figure 81 European Lidar Market size, by product type, 2020–2030 (USD millions)

In 2021 the global LIDAR market was dominated by North America with a revenue share of 36.6%. The biggest growth opportunities of North America’s market come from the automotive sector with the increasing adoption of the

advanced driver-assistance system and automatic emergency braking. On a market application level, as seen in **Figure 82**, the largest market is predicted to be in Corridor Mapping, followed by Engineering applications, Environmental uses, Exploration, ADAS and others, with the global application market size estimated to be USD 1.8 billion in 2021.

Figure 82 Global LiDAR Market share, by application, 2021

APAC is forecast to be the fastest-growing region from 2022 to 2030, growing annually 14.4% as there is increasing number of surveying and mapping operations in the region. China and India are considered as profitable markets thanks to the growing financing by the local and overseas players.

3D Printed Buildings

The 3D printed buildings Market is relatively new, with small market sizes estimated in 2021 (USD 0.04 Billion), but is predicted to experience massive growth up to 2024, with a CAGR predicted of 315.3, as seen in **Figure 83**. This market growth is predicted to arise from the growing demand for mass customization of buildings and enhanced architectural flexibility in building activities. By far. The building sector is the major end use sector in the 3d printing construction market, with market demand globally in all regions. On a square meter basis, as in the square meters produced via 3d printed building methods, huge growth is also predicted, growing from an estimate 7,548.9 square meters in 2019 to an estimated 9,326,642 square meters in 2024.

Figure 83 Global 3D Printed Buildings Markets 2019–2024

Segmentation by sector, **Figure 84**, again shows that the buildings sector will be the dominate area, with huge, predicted growth rates of 324.3% CGR between 2019 and 2024. While still showing a large predicted CARG or 286.8% to 2024, the use of 3d printing for infrastructure will be much lower than for buildings. Interestingly, this space saw no market demand or activity prior to 2019, making it a brand-new sector, prime for innovation and activity.

Source: Expert Interviews, Secondary Literature, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 84 3D Printed Buildings Sectoral Share to 2024

Geographically, the 3D printed building market growth rates and key regions to 2024, as seen in **Figure 85**, is predicted to be led by Saudi Arabia (440%) and UAE (423.8%), with significant growth also seen in China (247.5%), Russia (230%), El Salvador (224%) and France (220%), with significant growth rates also found in many European, North American and Asia Pacific countries.

Figure 85 Global 3D Printed Buildings Market Growth Rates

The market dynamics of the 3D Printing Construction Market (Table 9) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 9 Market Dynamics for 3D Printing Construction Market

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potential for mass customization and enhanced architectural flexibility ● Reduction in health and safety risks and rate of accidents ● Inherently green technology
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High capital investment
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rise in demand for new construction across region ● Rapid urbanization
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase the awareness about automation techniques in the construction industry ● Smooth surface finish ● Limited size of printers ● Partially-built houses

Digital Transformation Market

The global digital transformation Market has been growing rapidly since the proliferation of technology in businesses, with the digital transformation market estimated in 2022, with projections made out to 2027, indicating an average CAGR of 21.1% from a market size of US 594,472 million in 2022 to an estimated US 1,548,912 million by 2027 [42], as in **Figure 86**. The growth of this market is fuelled by the demand for tools which combine several heterogenous data sources and a growing adoption of cloud computing, generating demand for more effective digital transformation technologies and services. The largest region of potential is North America, with the fastest growing end user base existing in the healthcare, life sciences and pharmaceutical sectors. The largest market is present in the large enterprise sector, with that market hare relatively unchanged up to 2027. While enterprise is the largest sector, significant opportunity exists in the small to medium enterprise sector also, representing about 1/3 of the total market availability, as seen in **Figure 87**.

Figure 86 Digital Transformation Market Size 2022 and 2027 [42]

Figure 87 Digital transformation market, by organization size (USD, millions) [42]

Segmentation by deployment type, as seen in **Figure 88** in 2022 shows that Cloud and On Premises deployments are relatively level at approximate USD 200000 million, with huge grow estimated in Cloud deployment by 2027 to a value in excess of USD 550000 million, with slightly smaller growth predicted for onsite deployments to in excess of USD 450000 million by 2027 [42].

Figure 88 Digital Transformation Market, by deployment (USD million) [42]

Segmentation by business function, as seen in **Figure 89**, shows that the largest sector and growth is predicted in the Sales and Marketing Function, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 500000 million by 2027, up from a market size of just over USD 200000 million in 2022. All other business functions are predicted to double up to 2027, with largest market established in the Information technology (over USD 250000 million), Other Business Functions (over USD 300000 million), Accounting and Finance (over USD 200000 million) and Human Resource Management (over USD 200000 million) [42].

Figure 89 Digital Transformation Market, by business function (USD million) [42]

Segmentation by technology, as seen in **Figure 90**, shows that the largest technology driver is predicted to be Mobility and Social Media Management, with a predicted market size in excess of USD 300000 million by 2027, up from a market size of just over USD 125000 million in 2022. All other technology enablers are predicted to grow significantly up to 2027, with largest additional growth in the Cloud Computing (over USD 250000 million), Big Data Analytics (over USD 240000 million), Cyber Security (over USD 275000 million), AI (over USD 260000 million) and IoT (over USD 90000 million) technologies.

Figure 90 Digital Transformation Market, by technology (USD million) [42]

Geographically, growth in the digital transformation market, as seen in Figure 91, will be led on a total market size basis by North America, growing to a market of USD 451508 million in 2027 (at a CAGR of 18%) and on a CAGR basis by Asia-Pacific at a 23.6% rate (to a market size of USD 398070 million) to 2027. Smaller growth rates will be seen in Europe, USD 405815 million and CAGR of 21.6% to 2027, in Middle East and Africa, USD 165724 million and CAGR of 21.9% to 2027 and finally in South America, USD 127785 million and CAGR of 23.1% to 2027.

REGION	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	CAGR
ASIA-PACIFIC	137,918.0	164,841.0	200,300.0	249,414.0	314,381.0	398,070.0	23.6 %
SOUTH AMERICA	45,227.0	53,904.0	65,387.0	81,287.0	101,675.0	127,785.0	23.1 %
MIDDLE EAST AND AFRICA	61,528.0	72,335.0	86,493.0	106,026.0	132,240.0	165,734.0	21.9 %
EUROPE	152,779.0	179,448.0	214,370.0	262,541.0	325,609.0	405,815.0	21.6 %
NORTH AMERICA	197,020.0	225,005.0	261,134.0	310,506.0	373,639.0	451,508.0	18 %
TOTAL	594,472.0	695,533.0	827,684.0	1,009,774.0	1,247,543.0	1,548,912.0	21.1 %

Figure 91 Digital Transformation Market, by region, 2022 - 2027 (USD million) [42]

The market dynamics of the Digital Transformation Market (

Table 10) are influenced by a number of core factors including:

Table 10 Market Dynamics for Digital Transformation Market [42]

Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising adoption of big data and other related technologies • Advent of ML and digital transformation • Cost benefits of cloud-based digital transformation solutions • Rapid proliferation of mobile devices and apps • Adoption and scaling of digital initiatives
Restraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing regional data regulations to lead to time-consuming restructuring of predictive models • Data security concerns • Issues about privacy and security of information
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising internet proliferation and growing usage of connected and integrated technologies • Demand for personalised digital transformation • Increasing willingness of organizations to use digital technology
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues related to IT modernisation • Integration of data from data silos • Ownership and privacy of collected data

13. Appendix 2

Figure 92 to Figure 94 show the PESTEL analyses for UC Cat1 to UC Cat3, respectively.

Figure 92 Use Case 1 PESTEL Analysis

Figure 93 Use Case 2 PESTEL Analysis

Figure 94 Use Case 3 PESTEL Analysis